

Neo-Assyrian Women, Their Visibility, and Their Representation in Written and Pictorial Sources

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*You should be women,
And yet your beards forbid me to interpret
That you are so.*

—William Shakespeare, *Macbeth*

1. *Matters of Methodology*

Feminist scholarship launched a search for women in human history. As soon as one starts looking for women, they are inevitably found. Neither women nor gender were invisible in the past. In terms of the Neo-Assyrian period, the rich textual material collected by Saana Svård exemplifies how numerous our written sources are on the Neo-Assyrian women.¹

Nonetheless, with the further development of gender studies the following questions arise.² What methods should we apply to our sources? What aspects of gender were chosen for representation? Which were consciously suppressed and why? Svård examines the rich evidence she has assembled from the important aspect of its relation to power, and there is no doubt that research should be continued in this direction. The interdisciplinary comparative investigation into the diachronic changes in the status of women over the entire course of Mesopotamian history is definitely a promising direction of investigation.

The correct evaluation of sources concerning women is an essential methodological concern, and here comparison is useful not only when applied interdisciplinary. Tallay Ornan writes: “Assuming that visibility . . . serves as one parameter for the political, social, or cultural status of the depicted figure, one may conclude that royal women in first-millennium Assyria were devoid of official political, social or religious power.”³ This statement is based on Ornan’s assumption that “the few

1. Svård 2015. Svård has collected, arranged in easily accessible form, and thoroughly analyzed all the Neo-Assyrian sources related to royal women. Svård’s *Women and Power in Neo-Assyrian Palaces* naturally encompasses only high-ranking women. Numerous sources on women of lower status still await research. There are only two other monographs regarding Neo-Assyrian women (Melville 1999 and Macgregor 2012). However, they do not embrace the entire range of existing sources on Neo-Assyrian royal women, because that was not the focus of their investigation. Valuable information on Neo-Assyrian women can be also found in the monograph by W. Meinhold dedicated to Istar of Assur (Meinhold 2009). A discussion of Neo-Assyrian women is found also in Melville 2004.

2. See Bahrani 2001: 1–39 for an overview of the role of feminist scholarship, postmodernism, and poststructuralism in gender studies.

3. Ornan 2002: 464.

depictions of royal women, however, should be seen as part of more representational works of art, probably comparable to the depictions of their male consort, the king.⁴

Is it methodologically correct to compare the visibility of women, royal or otherwise, to that of the king? As is shown below, regarding Assyria, comparing the visibility of the queen to that of the king is very misleading; it is also not a fruitful methodological approach. The king was the main and almost the only protagonist of both pictorial and verbal narratives in any period of Neo-Assyrian history. Consequently, a comparison of frequency of appearance for any official, including the queen as such, with that of the king should not be applied to written or pictorial sources, because the king will always be represented far more often. I would like to highlight the profound fallacy of approaching the visibility of the queen in relation to the visibility of the king, in conjunction not only with pictorial sources but written material in the first place.⁵ If we compare the visibility of royal women with the visibility of the king's magnates, it becomes clear that the former were not at all invisible.⁶

2. Correspondence⁷

Based on correspondence only, it is easy to demonstrate that one should not compare the king and the queen. Interestingly, however, it appears that the number of letters written by all the Assyrian kings, starting from Tiglath-pileser (744–727 B.C.E.) through Sīn-šarru-iškun (627?–612 B.C.E.), is not very large—76 letters only.⁸ Princes sent altogether 34 letters.⁹ Nonetheless, there is only one letter by a royal woman, the letter written by Šērū'a-ētirat to her lazy sister-in-law Libbāli-šarrat.¹⁰ The overwhelming majority of Neo-Assyrian letters (about 2,301) address the king.¹¹

4. Ornan 2002: 463.

5. Because I was initially trained as both an Assyriologist and archaeologist, I always thoroughly explore the whole body of relevant written and pictorial sources in my research, here and elsewhere. I am glad that this approach is also applied in some other contributions in this volume (e.g., Pinnock's). All of the written sources in this contribution are related, however, to royal or noble women exclusively.

6. I do not discuss documents and the nonmonumental inscriptions here, because their relevance for the question of visibility needs further discussion, and this is beyond the scope of this essay.

7. It is my pleasure to draw the attention of the reader to the excellent publications of the Helsinki Neo-Assyrian Texts Corpus Project, where all the personal and geographical names used here can be found, namely, the *Prosopography of the Neo-Assyrian Empire* (Radner and Baker 1998–2011) and *The Helsinki Atlas of the Near East in the Neo-Assyrian Period* (Parpola and Porter 2001).

8. SAA 1 1–28, SAA 5 277–81, SAA 13 1–7, SAA 16 1–13, SAA 17 1–6, SAA 18 1–5, SAA 19 1–7 (Tiglath-pileser III), SAA 19 152–56 (Sargon). For a chronological distribution of the Neo-Assyrian royal correspondence, see Mattila and Harjumäki 2015: 13, chart 1; and May 2015: 94 n. 74.

9. All the letters of princes, where it is possible to establish the addressee, are written to the king, with the exception of SAA 18 6, 7. These are 4 letters of Ulūlāiu (SAA 19 8–11), 14 of Sennacherib (SAA 1 29–40, SAA 5 281 and SAA 19 158), 7 of Assurbanipal (SAA 16 14–20), 6 of Šamaš-šumu-ukīn (SAA 16 21–24 and SAA 18 6, 7), and 3 of Šamaš-mētu-uballit (SAA 16 25–27).

10. SAA 16 28. The matter might be simple—royal women lived in palaces, and if they sent letters it was to the outside. In general, there are very few letters written by women (besides SAA 16 28, these are SAA 16 49, SAA 19 144, KAV 170, and probably SAA 18 117) and only two directly to the king: one was sent by Barsipītu, a female representative of Babylonian nobility (SAA 17 73), and the other probably by Borsippean noble women (SAA 16 153). The reason seems to be clear: women did not have positions either in the king's administration or as scholars. What is surprising is that we do not know of any Assyrian priestesses. See also Neo-Assyrian female letters in Halton and Svärd (2018: 149–52) for a recent translation and discussion of these letters.

11. This is an approximate number, because when the greeting formula is broken away it is not always possible to establish the addressee with certainty. All of the numbers here are based on the correspondence found in the palaces at Assyrian capitals and published by the SAA series.

Judging from the governor's archive discovered at Kalḫu,¹² the officials had their archives stored in their offices. The archives stored at Kalḫu and Nineveh were royal *par excellence*. With a few exceptions, the letters written to officials were written by the king himself. Obviously, our criteria of the prominence of a certain person also include the number of letters that the person received which were not from the king.

Among the letters not written by the king or to the king are nine cases that can be identified with certainty as written to the queen-mother, Naqī'a, by scholars, priests, and officials.¹³ Other high-ranking women who received letters are Libbāli-šarrat¹⁴ (then the wife of the crown prince), Šērū'a-ēṭirat herself,¹⁵ and a certain lady Baṭi-lēšir, addressed as a male (EN-ia 'my lord'), as was usually the case with the queen-mother.¹⁶ Each of them received one letter. The addressee of SAA 18 102 might also be Naqī'a, as suggested by its editors.

Among the officials, the recipients of letters not from the king in the time of Tiglath-pileser III and the time of Sargon include:

- a palace scribe of Tiglath-pileser III, who received 1 letter¹⁷
- Sīn-aḫu-ušur, the *sukkallu* of Sargon and Sennacherib, Sargon's brother, received 19 letters¹⁸
- Tāb-šar-Aššūr, the chamberlain of Sargon (*masennu*)—3 letters¹⁹
- a certain Nabū-dūru-ušur—3 letters²⁰
- Sargon's governor, presumably Aššūr-bāni, the governor of Kalḫu—1 letter²¹
- Sennacherib as crown prince received only 1 letter²²
- a palace herald (*nāgir ekalli*)—1 letter (but from Urzana, king of Mušāšir!)²³

2. There is one letter from the time of Sennacherib:

- the chief eunuch (*rab ša rēši*) received 1 letter from Bēl-ibni, the puppet-king of Sennacherib in Babylonia in 703–700 B.C.E.²⁴

3. In the times of Esarhaddon and Assurbanipal, there are 21 letters not written to or by the king:

- the king's son (most probably Assurbanipal, but possibly also Šamaš-šumu-ukīn) received 11 letters²⁵

12. Postgate 1973.

13. SAA 10 16, 17, 154, 313; SAA 13 76, 77, 188; SAA 18 10, 85. Naqī'a also received a letter from the king (SAA 16 2). SAA 13 94 was probably also written to Naqī'a (see Svärd 2015: 204).

14. The aforementioned letter of Šērū'a-ēṭirat.

15. SAA 18 55.

16. SAA 16 56.

17. SAA 19 56.

18. SAA 1 123, 191; SAA 5 168; SAA 15 138, 169; SAA 17 20, 21, 64, 66, 77, 78, 95, 132, 136, 141, 142?, 177. SAA 17 177 was probably addressed to both the king and the vizier (see rev. 2–6), SAA 19 142. See May 2014: 482 for the date of the latter; see also May 2018: 495–96, 506–14, for the discussion of the correspondence of Sargon's *sukkallu*.

19. SAA 5 96, 97, 110.

20. SAA 1 215, 220, 221.

21. SAA 19 160.

22. SAA 1 153.

23. SAA 5 147.

24. SAA 17 53.

25. SAA 10 136, 180, 182, 186, 195; SAA 13 78, 158; SAA 16 69, 70, 116, 124.

- 4 letters of priests and 3 of scholars to each other²⁶
- *Sukkallu* of Esarhaddon, presumably a royal kin, receives one letter.²⁷
- 2 letters sent to family members residing in the palace²⁸

If we compare the number of letters received by royal officials, we find that Sargon II's powerful vizier and brother Sīn-aḥu-uṣur received 19 letters, Naqī'a received 9 letters, and all the crown princes together received only 22. Other addressees received an insignificant amount. The amount of correspondence addressed to the king incomparably exceeds that of all his magnates, but the latter are also far behind Sargon's vizier and Naqī'a. It should be stressed, however, that both the cases of Sīn-aḥu-uṣur and Naqī'a are exceptional. Their personal qualities and abilities doubtlessly played an important role in their promotion, but the main factor was nonetheless their blood relationship and devotion to the king. In any case, Naqī'a is certainly not invisible in the royal correspondence in comparison to the magnates.

3. Monumental Inscriptions

The installation of monuments such as steles, inscriptions and palace reliefs was a royal prerogative. Assyrian royal monumental inscriptions are extensive and countless, and no official, including the queen, can rival a king in terms of the number, length, and elaboration of inscriptions. However, the inscriptions of queens and magnates are comparable, and an investigation into them reveals interesting diachronic patterns. The monumental inscriptions related to queens and magnates can be divided into the following categories, according to their relevance for the significance of the official they relate to:²⁹

1. monuments established by queens or magnates themselves in capitals and provinces³⁰
2. monuments established together with the king
3. monuments established in the name of the king
4. monuments of the king which mention queens and magnates
5. dedicatory monumental inscriptions (by magnates for the health of the king, queens, and themselves)

26. *Priests*: SAA 13 39, 40, 41, 42. *Scholars*: SAA 10 183, 372, 384.

27. SAA 18 21. For *sukkallus'* of Sargonids relationship to the royal family, see May 2018: 494–96, 515–18.

28. SAA 18 97 and 117.

29. Some of the inscriptions of the magnates discussed below are building inscriptions. No monumental building inscriptions by the queens are known. The inscriptions of Naqī'a, usually interpreted as her building the palace for her son Esarhaddon (RINAP 4 2003–2004) are not monumental, like those of Sīn-aḥu-uṣur, but written on clay prism and cylinder. In contrast, there are no building inscriptions of magnates on the clay prisms or cylinders. Apparently, this is due to the fact that writing on these media in the Neo-Assyrian period only starts with Sargon (see May 2015: 95–96), while no inscriptions of magnates are known from the time of Sargon or his successors apart from those of Sargon's brother Sīn-aḥu-uṣur. Sargon II's prism inscription from Tell Baradān that commemorates the construction of the city wall of Mē-Turān, mentions Nabū-bēl-ka³⁰in, governor of Arrapha (Kessler 2003–2004, line 15').

30. It is important to stress that, as opposed to the monuments installed by the queens themselves, which are known only from the capitals, and the monuments of the magnates, which were installed in their provinces exclusively or in the *Stelenreihe*, the monuments of the kings were installed all over the Assyrian Empire and even beyond: in capitals, provinces, vassal states, and outmost territories reached by the Assyrian army. Thus, the royal steles were installed even in the territories that did not remain within the empire.

Figure 1. The stele of Libbāli-šarrat. After Andrae 1913: 7, fig. 3 and pl. 10.

3.1. Queens

1. *Monuments established by queens themselves in the capitals.* There are three steles in the so-called *Stelenreihe* at Assur. The queens Sammu-rāmat³¹ and Libbāli-šarrat (fig. 1),³² as well as the unknown queen(-mother?) of Sennacherib,³³ installed their steles in the *Stelenreihe* in the same row as the kings. Only the stele of Sammu-rāmat was found *in situ*. The stele of Libbāli-šarrat was found in the post-imperial building; it was apparently in secondary use as a floor pavement. The stele of Sennacherib's queen was also removed from its original place, probably deliberately, as was its inscription. The name of Sennacherib's queen, which was chiseled away, was a subject of *damnatio memoriae*. Nonetheless, all the steles were unearthed at the utmost west end of the row of royal steles, which may have been reserved for the steles of the queens.³⁴ These steles are the only monuments

31. Andrae 1913: 10–11, no. 5, pl. 11, 2; RIMA 3 A.0.104.2001.

32. Andrae 1913: 6–8, no. 1.

33. Andrae 1913: 9–19, no. 4, and RINAP 3/2 2001 follow Frahm 2014: 179 with references to the previous editions. For a discussion of the most recent suggestion for reading the inscription on the stele, see Frahm (2014: 179). Neither the name (of which only the feminine determinative is clearly preserved) nor the title can be read with certainty, but all known inscriptions of the Assyrian queens always state them as being MUNUS.É.GAL ('palace women = the queen') of their husband the king. The other titles, such as the mother of the king always follow after MUNUS.É.GAL. If the reading suggested by E. Weissert and followed by E. Frahm (2014: 179) is correct and only AMA ('mother') appears on the stele in question, this queen is the only one who did not designate her marital status.

34. See Andrae 1913: 6–8, 9–11, and pls. 1, 3; and Reade 2004: 463–64 for the find spots and other details of the discovery of the queens' steles. J. Reade notes that three unidentified steles (nos. 2, 3 and 19) may have also belonged to the queens as well as to the kings (Reade 2004: 463–64).

established by the queens themselves, as so far no steles established by the queens in the provinces are known.

2. *Sammu-rāmat, the queen-mother, was the co-installer of the stele, together with the king.*³⁵

3. *No monuments installed by queens in the name of the king are known.*

4. *Monuments of the king that mention queens.* Sennacherib's building inscription related to the construction of the quarters of his queen Tašmētu-šarrat was incised on the sphinxes (found *in situ*) which flanked the entrance to this queen's quarters.³⁶ A gypsum block with part of an epitaph of Ešarra-ḥammāt also belonged to a monumental inscription, judging from the size of the surviving fragment (44 × 39 cm).³⁷ A bronze relief representing the king, presumably Esarhaddon, describes the mouth-washing (*mīs pī*) ritual apparently related to Esarhaddon's restoration of the statues of Babylonian gods; it contains images of the king and the queen. The epigraph on the queen's gown identifies her as Naqī'a.³⁸

5. *Dedicatory inscriptions (of the queens for the health of the king or their own life).* No monumental dedicatory inscriptions of the queens are known. All of the rather rare dedicatory inscriptions of the queens concern different kinds of jewelry.³⁹

3.2. *Magnates*

1. *Monuments established by magnates themselves.* In the religious capital, these include the steles in the *Stelenreihe* at Assur. From the row of Neo-Assyrian officials, only 10 steles are preserved.⁴⁰ All of these steles belonged to eponymous officials.⁴¹ 166 eponyms are known from 910 to 744 B.C.E., the start of the reign of Tiglath-pileser III; thus, the number of the magnates who installed their steles in the *Stelenreihe* or whose steles survived constitutes only about 6% of the known eponyms.⁴² These steles of officials list their titles, sometimes at length, but never mention the king. Sin-aḫu-ušur, the brother of Sargon II, was the only magnate who

35. RIMA 3 A.O.104.3, from Pazarḡik.

36. RINAP 3/2 40 44"b—46".

37. RINAP 4 2002 (Ass. 1). This inscription preserves a fragment of the epitaph of this queen.

38. RINAP 4 2010 with related description and references.

39. These are the "eye-stone" of Sammu-rāmat (Seymour 2008: 104), the inscriptions of Naqī'a-Zaqūtu—all for the life and well-being of Esarhaddon (RINAP 4 2005–8), and a votive text of the queen of Assurbanipal, probably Libbāli-šarrat, dedicating a golden object for the life and security of reign of Assurbanipal and her own life (Deller 1983: 22–24; this is a non-monumental inscription on a clay tablet). The queen also asked the goddess to make the king attentive to her words. Moreover, a stone jar was dedicated by Inūrta-abūni, sister of Assurnaširpal II (ASV 615). Remarkably, all of these objects were dedicated to female deities.

40. These are the steles of Nergal-āpil-kūmū'a (no. 50, 673 B.C.E.), Issār-emūqāia (no. 99, 867 B.C.E.), Šamaš-bēlu-ušur (no. 42, 851 B.C.E.), Inūrta-kibsī-ušur (no. 47, 838 B.C.E.), Šarru-Ḥattu-ipella (no. 41, 815 B.C.E.), Ilu-ittīja (no. 38, 804 B.C.E.), Marduk-šimanni (no. 39, 799 B.C.E.), Bēlu-lū-balaṭ (no. 44, 814 B.C.E.), *turtānu* and *nāgīru rabīu* of Šamši-Adad V; see also RIMA 3 A.O.102.2002), Aplāia (no. 34, 768 B.C.E.), and Adad-bēlu-ka²in (no. 37, 748 B.C.E.). See Andrae 1913: 46–54, 75–76.

41. Already W. Andrae suggested that the row served as an eponym list (Millard 1994: 12; Reade 2004: 464). Despite the skepticism of P. Miglus (1984: 138) and his own reservations, J. Reade reascertained Andrae's suggestion (2004: 464, 468–70). Reade further suggests that steles nos. 29, 30, 31, 33, 35, 36, 40, 43, 45 (the inscriptions on which did not survive) also belonged to eponym officials (2004: 466–67).

42. None of the steles of officials in the *Stelenreihe* are later than 748 B.C.E. I discuss whether the practice of installation of the steles in the *Stelenreihe* by the magnates was ceased by Tiglath-pileser or by Sargon below.

left monumental inscriptions in an acting royal capital (at that point Dūr-Šarrukīn). That was not a stele but a floor inscription—or, more precisely, three almost identical inscriptions⁴³ incised into the stone carpets of the thresholds of Sīn-aḥu-uṣur's palace (Palace L) at Dūr-Šarrukīn, which was built next to the royal residence in the new capital.⁴⁴ The inscription celebrates the inauguration of Sīn-aḥu-uṣur's palace.⁴⁵

2. *There are also a number of monumental inscriptions in provinces.* Šamšī-ilu⁴⁶ and Bēl-Ḥarrān-bēlu-uṣur⁴⁷ dared to erect their own monumental inscriptions in their own provinces of Til Barsib and Gūzāna, respectively. The lion inscriptions of Šamšī-ilu were severely erased. In form they are dedicatory inscriptions, although Šamšī-ilu only lists the gods to whom they were dedicated and does not state the purpose of the dedication.⁴⁸ Inūrta-bēlu-uṣur, the governor of Kār-Salmānu-ašarēd and eunuch of Šamšī-ilu, installed bilingual and (so far unique) trilingual inscriptions, which were incised on the gate lions at Ḥadattu. These rather short inscriptions celebrate his building of that city.⁴⁹ Two inscriptions probably belong to Šamšī-ilu as well, but their text is too broken to establish this with certainty.⁵⁰ Finally, Mušēzib-Šamaš, a district governor⁵¹ of Dūru, installed a stele similar to a royal one in his city (fig. 2). The inscription is quite damaged and not always clear, but it is evident that the installer dedicated it to Adad to secure his long life and position.⁵² What is important is that this stele bears a similar representation to that of Bēl-Ḥarrān-bēlu-uṣur, with both steles imitating royal ones. The stele was broken, and the inscription, as well as the face and hands of Mušēzib-Šamaš's figure, is badly damaged.⁵³ It is worth noting that all of these inscriptions were located in the West and found within approximately 150 km of each other.

3. *No monuments co-installed by a king and magnates are known.*

4. *All the other so-called inscriptions of the magnates were installed in the name of the king, though they describe the deeds of the magnates.* It sounds as though Šamšī-ilu was the co-installer of a boundary stone, the Antakya stele, with the king,⁵⁴ but unlike the Pazarḡik inscription of Adad-nērārī and Sammu-rāmat, the opening phrase of the Antakya inscription contains only the genealogy and the epithets of the king, not of Šamšī-ilu.⁵⁵ The stele also bears a figurative representation, but its upper part is broken, and it is impossible to establish who is represented. On the

43. Sīn-aḥu-uṣur's inscriptions most probably date to 707 or 706 B.C.E. because this relates to the time after the inauguration of the Dūr-Šarrukīn temples, and Palace L should have been finished before the inauguration of the city in 706 B.C.E. (Eponym Chronicle; Millard 1994: 48).

44. See Meissner 1944: 37–38; Loud and Altman 1938: 104; May 2012a: 199–200; May 2018: 498–99.

45. On this inscription as a Palace L inauguration inscription, see Hurowitz 2014: 93–94 with n. 21.

46. RIMA 3 A.0.104.2010.

47. RIMA A.0.105.2. For the image see Börker-Klähn 1982: no. 232.

48. RIMA 3 A.0.104.2010.

49. Röllig 2009, especially pp. 268–69, 271–72, 276; Hawkins 2000a: 246–48. Arbitrarily treated in RINAP 1 2001 together with the inscriptions of Tiglath-pileser III.

50. RIMA 3 A.0.104.2011, purchase; RIMA 3 A.0.104.2012?, from Assur.

51. As *bēl piḥāti* he was neither a province governor nor a magnate.

52. The inscription was not recently treated. For its photograph, see Pognon 1907: pl. 5; for hand-copies, see Pognon 1907: pl. 26 and pp. 106–7; for editions, see pp. 106–7 with n.1 and Meissner 1908: 242–43.

53. The stele was probably never finished because the divine symbols are absent.

54. RIMA 3 A.0.104.2 4–8a.

55. RIMA 3 A.0.104.2 1–3.

back of the Pazarġik stele of Adad-nērārī III and Sammu-rāmat, found near Mar^cāš, the inscription was incised in the name of Shalmaneser IV. Šamšī-ilu is the main protagonist of this boundary-stone inscription, which was actually written by him but in the name of the king, confirming the border established by Adad-nērārī III and Sammu-rāmat for Ušpilulume of Kummuḫi.⁵⁶ On the stele from Saba'a, also installed in the name of the king, the part of the inscription related to Pālil-ēreš (= Nergal-ēreš) was erased as well.⁵⁷ The famous Tall al-Rimāḥ stele was discovered in a temple cella beside the podium of the divine statue.⁵⁸

Figure 2. Stele of Mušēzib-Šamaš. After Pognon 1907: pl. 5.

After the royal titles and a rather short account of the king's military achievements⁵⁹ follow the titles of Pālil-ēreš and a list of cities added to his governorship by the king.⁶⁰ Pālil-ēreš is said to have rebuilt these cities "by the decree of his lord."⁶¹ Like on the Saba'a stele, the lines related to Pālil-ēreš were deliberately erased despite the curse that follows them.⁶² The imagery of all of these monuments is royal.

56. RIMA 3 A.0.105.1 11–13a and 1–3, written on the back of A.0.104.3.

57. RIMA 3 A.0.104.6 3–20.

58. RIMA 3 A.0.104.7.

59. RIMA 3 A.0.104.7, ll. 1–12.

60. RIMA 3 A.0.104.7, ll. 13–20.

61. *ina zi-kir* EN-šú; RIMA 3 A.0.104.7, l. 20.

62. RIMA 3 A.0.104.7, l. 21.

5. *Monuments of the king that mention magnates.* Daiān-Aššūr is mentioned in the inscription of the Black Obelisk and another inscription of Shalmaneser III on his badly broken statue, both from Kalḫu.⁶³

6. *There are also monumental inscriptions dedicated by the magnates for the life of the king or their own lives.*⁶⁴ The magnates themselves installed these monuments. Two identical and relatively long inscriptions by Bēl-tarṣi-ilumma, the governor of Kalḫu and a scribe during a previous stage of his career, were incised with a dedication to Nabû on two identical statues of this god found in the Nabû Temple at Kalḫu. The dedication was made for the life of King Adad-nērārī III and Queen Sammu-rāmat in the first place, and only then was a dedication made for the life of the donor himself, the well-being of his household, and the health of his people. These inscriptions do not extol the military or the building activities of Bēl-tarṣi-ilumma.⁶⁵ Quite extraordinary is the dedicatory inscription of Pāli-ēreš to the god Salmānu of Dūr-Katlimmu, incised on the lefthand side of a royal stele with a standard royal inscription.⁶⁶ This inscription of Pāli-ēreš dedicates the image of Adad-nērārī III, apparently the stele itself, for the well-being and prosperity of the king, the dynasty, Assyria, and so forth. The name and titles of Pāli-ēreš were erased. A very short inscription of only one sentence was made by Aššur-dūr-pānīa, Sargon II's governor of Til-Barsib, on a stele apparently installed by him in his province. It is a dedication to Ištār of Arbail for his own life, and it bears an image of the goddess in warrior attire standing on a lion.⁶⁷ The steles with divine images are of Syrian rather than Neo-Assyrian type.⁶⁸

The magnates could install inscriptions of their own in their provinces, even if at Kalḫu. The phenomenon is limited chronologically to the period of the great influence and maybe the factual rule of Šamši-ilu, that is, the reign of Adad-nērārī III and his heirs (810–744? B.C.E.).⁶⁹ To some extent, the magnates of Tiglath-pileser III reserved this right as well. Moreover, Šamši-ilu also installed two boundary stones in the name of the king. He is the only one who, at least in a way, followed the example of Sammu-rāmat's Pazarḡik stele; he installed a stele not in his own province but in its vicinity. Remarkably, the inscriptions of his Antakya and Pazarḡik stele were written in the name of the king. Notably, the queens as installers and co-installers of monumental inscriptions were in a more privileged position than the magnates. Three inscriptions of the queens come from the *Stelenreihe*, from the *royal row*, while 10 are of the magnates.⁷⁰ The latter steles are not from the royal row. If the

63. RIMA 3 A.0.102.14 141b–156a, 159b–190; and RIMA 3 A.0.102.16 228'–244', 268'–286'a, 291'–341'a. The camp of Taklāk-ana-Bēl appears in the epigraph of the room 14 relief of Sargon's palace at Dūr-Šarrukīn (Fuchs 1994: 279, 14.10.1). Although now restored with certainty, the name of the magnate was destroyed except for one partially preserved sign.

64. It seems to have been a special privilege to be granted permission to dedicate inscriptions, steles, or statues for the life of the king and queen.

65. RIMA 3 A.0.104.2002. This is the only dedication for the life of both the king and the queen (-mother). The only comparable document is SAA 12 96, where two slaves and an estate are donated by Nabû-sakip to Nabû for the life of Šin-šarru-iškun, king of Assyria, his lord, and for the life of his queen.

66. Found at Dūr-Katlimmu; Radner 2012a: 272–73, Siddall 2013: 192–98.

67. Found at Til-Barsib; Radner 2006: 186.

68. See p. 259 below with n. 75 for the exceptions.

69. See Fuchs 2008 for a discussion.

70. Despite the severe iconoclasm of Šamši-ilu's monuments (Fuchs 2008: 96–97; May 2010: 111), to suggest that his stele was removed from the *Stelenreihe* would be pure speculation.

Figure 3. The Garden Scene relief. Enthroned Libbāli-šarrat celebrating with Assurbanipal. Photograph by N. N. May.

right to install steles in Assur was indeed reserved for eponymous officials, a very small number of their inscriptions were preserved. The practice of installing steles of officials at Assur stopped in the middle of the eighth century, which in my opinion was part of Sargon’s administrative reforms and his program of diminishing the power and liberties of the magnates.⁷¹ Queens had never been eponyms in Assyria, and their right to install steles in the royal row was a matter of the policy of their king, as well as, probably, the role they played in state affairs. The same seems to be correct for the magnates who installed their steles in the *Stelenreihe*.

With the exception of Sammu-rāmat, all of the monumental inscriptions of the queens come from the time of the Sargonids—that is, exactly when the magnates could no longer install their own monuments. The steles of Sammu-rāmat and Sennacherib’s queen are similar in form and content to those of the magnates. They only bear short inscriptions, stating that it is an “image,” not an actual depiction. From this point on, the monuments of Naqī’a⁷² and Libbāli-šarrat differ dramatically. Like the royal monuments, they do bear representations of these queens.⁷³

71. See May 2012a: 194; 2015.

72. See pp. 253–254 above with nn. 34, 38.

73. See May 2012a: 223, fig. 8.17 for a bronze relief with Naqī’a’s image and figs. 1 and 3 for the stele of Libbāli-šarrat and the Garden Scene. For a detailed discussion of these monuments, see the next section.

As the king's consorts, the Sargonid queens became part of the royal establishment. The case of Sin-aḫu-ušur as a member of the royal family is similar to that of the queens from this point. The case of Sammu-rāmat was surely part of the phenomenon of the independence of magnates in the times of Adad-nērārī III and Šamšī-ilu. Her monuments installed in Assur or co-installed with the king outrank even those of Šamšī-ilu. The installation of monumental inscriptions by Sargonid queens is unparalleled.

4. Monumental Representations⁷⁴

Humans depicted in monuments such as steles and palace reliefs merit a separate investigation in this essay. Due to huge anthropomorphic representations, the king's figure visually overshadows even the gods, who are depicted in miniature and mostly symbolic form on royal steles and rock reliefs.⁷⁵ But again, the appearance of queens in depictions should be compared to that of other officials, not to the king. Except for the crown prince, recognized due to his status signifier, the headband, not one of the numerous officials on the palace reliefs can be identified, either by name or by status. As for the Sargonids, their absolutism left very little space for representation of any power.⁷⁶ However, ostensibly few *monumental* figural depictions of queens derive exactly from the Sargonid period. These are the aforementioned representation of Naqī'a together with the king on a huge bronze relief (the dimensions of the fragment are 33 × 31 × 6.5 cm)⁷⁷ and two famous images of the enthroned Libbāli-šarrat—the Garden Scene relief (fig. 3), as well as her stele mentioned above (fig. 1). It should be stressed that all three representations are firmly identified as depicting queens not only by a status signifier, the mural crown, but also by

74. Uninscribed imagery of the magnates (Börker-Klähn 1982, nos. 237, 242, and 254) is not treated here, because of the impossibility of attributing it. However, Börker-Klähn 1982, nos. 242 and 254, which are reminiscent of steles and were treated as such by J. Börker-Klähn, are not monumental (19 × 12 and 30 × 35 cm, respectively). The bearded figure of no. 242 has an edge-band or a rim and a protrusion on the top of his headgear, which is reminiscent of the golden headgear found in the queen tombs (Curtis et al. 2008: pl. 5a). The rock relief belongs to the series found near Antakya (Börker-Klähn 1982: 230–32, nos. 236–39), and it might indeed represent Šamšī-ilu (Börker-Klähn 1982: 230–32, nos. 236–39). However, the face of the official on it is so badly damaged that it is impossible even to discern whether he is bearded or not. Close to monumental (height 1 m, width 1.6 m) is the Ergani/Gisgis rock relief. It depicts a eunuch and a king worshiping Ištar, who stands on a lion; a crescent, which is on a horse; and a winged disc, which is on a bull. The composition is very similar to that of the bronze relief of Naqī'a or the queen's chalcedony seal (May 2012a: 223, fig. 8.17; and fig. 5 in this essay), but the relief is uninscribed and of a very poor quality of execution. It is simply scratched on a very roughly smoothed surface of the rock (Koroğlu and Yumruk 2014: figs. 3–7). The relief was located at the outskirts of the Assyrian Empire, at the border of Bīt-Zamāni.

75. The exceptions are Bavian, Maltai (fig. 10 on p. 277), Assur, and some more reliefs of Sennacherib with anthropomorphic representations of gods slightly larger than the king (Börker-Klähn 1982: nos. 187–88, 205–10; Curtis and Reade 1995: figs. 7–17). On the Til Barsib and Sam'alla steles of Esarhaddon (Börker-Klähn 1982: nos. 217, 219; Jakob-Rost 1992: 180–82, nos. 116–18), the gods, though partly represented anthropomorphically, are still incomparably smaller than the figures of the king and his heirs.

76. The officials on the reliefs of Assurnasirpal II and Shalmaneser III are much more visible than on the reliefs of the Sargonids. They also have distinctive headbands, which were removed in Ḥorsābād and never appear again (see May 2012a: 205 n. 64; 2015: 110).

77. May 2012a: 223, fig. 8.17.

inscriptions; in the case of the bronze relief and the stele, this is done directly, and in the case of the Garden Scene indirectly by the neighboring epigraph.⁷⁸

On the bronze relief, both the queen and the king are represented in the *appa labānu* gesture.⁷⁹ The queen is crowned with a mural crown and wears a gown with a shawl—the status signifiers present also on depictions of Libbāli-šarrat. The label incised on the shawl perpendicular to the main inscription identifies her as Naqī'a. In her left hand, she holds a mirror. This is the only Neo-Assyrian representation where a mirror appears, but it has been shown already by Ornan that the mirror is a female attribute in Middle Assyrian, Hittite, as well as in Neo-Hittite and other Western representations.⁸⁰ In the case of Naqī'a, this attribute was adapted to depict the Assyrian queen and is otherwise unknown in Neo-Assyrian art. The surviving part of the main inscription describes the *mīs pī* ('mouth-washing') ritual performed in the temple of Ea at Babylon, in the Esagil complex.

The so-called Garden Scene relief from Room S of Assurbanipal's North Palace at Nineveh represents an enthroned queen with a mural crown and fancily decorated garment with a shawl, raising a bowl next to a reclining king identified as Assurbanipal (fig. 3). The epigraph above the nearby slab with a depiction of two Elamite kings bringing food to the banquet participants speaks about the celebration of the victory over Elam.⁸¹ The scene represents the triumph of 645 B.C.E. and the severed head hanging from the tree next to the banqueters is that of Nabû-bēl-šumāti, and not of Teumman, as is usually assumed.⁸² The queen is represented as seated on the luxuriously decorated throne with her legs on a footstool. A cloth is draped from the back of her seat. While her right hand raises a cup in a gesture of celebration (matching her king, Assurbanipal), her left hand holds a conic object which is similar to that of Esarhaddon on his Sam'alla stele.⁸³

The second representation of Libbāli-šarrat, her stele in the *Stelenreihe* at Assur, is identified due to this queen's inscription (fig. 1). This monument is extraordinary because it is the only Neo-Assyrian stele in *Stelenreihe* to bear an image.⁸⁴ Not only was it the case that the officials could not install steles in the *Stelenreihe* or anywhere else by the time when this queen's image was installed, but the spouse of Libbāli-šarrat, King Assurbanipal, also did not install a single stele.⁸⁵ Despite

78. The entire Garden Scene relief includes much more than the depiction of a wining and dining royal couple (Barnett 1976: pls. 63, 64, and F). For the epigraph, see n. 81 below.

79. May 2012a: 223, fig. 8.17. Note the similarity of the composition in Meli-Šipak's *kudurru* (Paulus 2014: 301) representation with that of the bronze relief and the queen's seal (fig. 5).

80. Ornan 2002: 471–72.

81. Gerardi 1988: 25:

[. . .] x [x x]-*ti-šú* SIG^{mes} *i-ram-mu gi-mir mal-ki šá* 'kiš'-[šat . . .]
 [. . .] x [. . .] 'LUGAL^{mes} šá KUR NIM.MA^{ki} šá ina KU-ti AN.ŠAR u ^dNIN.LÍL ik-šu-'da' šuⁱⁱ-[ia]
 [. . .] a? x [. . .]'zi'-zu-ma nap-tan MAN-ti-šú-nu šuⁱⁱ ra-me-ni-šú-nu e-pu-šá-ma ú-še-rib-u-ni ina [maḫrīia]

[. . .] his good (deeds?) they love, all the princes of the wor[ld . . .] kings of Elam, whom, with the encouragement of Assur and Ninlil, [my] hands conquered [. . .] they stood?, their royal meal they prepared with their own hands and they brought (it) [before me].

82. See May 2012b: 478–80 for discussion.

83. Börker-Klähn 1982: no. 219; Jakob-Rost 1992: 180–82, no. 116.

84. The only other figurative representation in the *Stelenreihe* is a badly damaged statue of the Middle Assyrian king (Andrae 1913: 14–18).

85. The only common characteristic of the so-called steles of Assurbanipal, which represent him as a basket-bearer (Börker-Klähn 1982: nos. 224–25), and Assyrian royal steles is their rounded shape at

Figure 4. Inscribed golden seal of Queen Ḥamâ. The queen is represented worshipping Mullissu/Ištar and wearing a tasseled headband. After May 2012a: 222, pl. 8.16.

Figure 5. Chalcedony queen's seal 2002-5-15, 1. Modern seal impression of the ancient seal. The king and the queen are represented worshipping Mullissu/Ištar. The queen is wearing a mural crown(?) and a tasseled headband. Copyright of the Trustees of the British Museum.

the fact that the image is not fully preserved, there is no doubt that the queen is represented as seated on the throne with a chain of beads or a cloth terminated by beaded embroidery hanging down the back of the throne, similarly to the Garden Scene. The queen's right hand is raised, and the left holds a flower.⁸⁶ The Western rulers such as Kilamuwa and Bar-Rakib of Sam'alla are represented on their steles with flowers in their left hands. Moreover, on some of these Western steles, the ruler holds both a flower and a cup.⁸⁷ Borrowing from the iconography of the Western steles was one of the ways to create iconography for queens. It is worth noting that there are no traces of representations of the gods or divine symbols on the surviving fragments of Libbāli-šarrat's stele. The iconography of the enthroned queen certainly copies that of Mullissu, the only Assyrian deity represented as enthroned (see figs. 1, 3, 4, 5, 10).⁸⁸

For comparison, there are only two identifiable images of the Neo-Assyrian officials known from monumental sources: the stele of the much disputed

the top. Both of Assurbanipal's "basket-bearer" monuments are not of monumental dimensions (35.9 × 22.2 cm and 39 × 15.5 cm). Both were installed in Babylonia, and their imagery imitates Neo-Sumerian foundation figurines (May 2013: 199–200). There is also pictorial evidence of the existence of a stele commemorating Assurbanipal's royal hunt (Barnett 1976: pls. 6 and A), the imagery of which is again not the traditional imagery of the Assyrian royal steles.

86. According to the original publication of Andrae 1913: pl. 10 and fig. 1 above.

87. Orthmann 1971: pl. 63, Zingirli E/2, F/1a, pl. 66, Zingirli K-1, K/2, J/2 (last two uninscribed). On F/4, K/2, and K/11, as well as on the recently discovered Kuttamuwa stele, the ruler has both the flower and the cup. There are also some uninscribed representations using the same attributes (Orthmann 1971: pl. 21 Karkamis Ab/4 and pl. 47 Mar'āš C/1). On what is probably the stele of Katuwas, the object in the hand of the ruler is broken, although it might be a flower (Orthmann 1971: pl.35 Karkamis K/28; Hawkins 2000a: 115–17; picture Hawkins 2000b: pl. 24).

88. Bavian relief (fig. 10, Börker-Klähn 1982: nos. 207–10; Curtis and Reade 1995: fig. 17), seal of Queen Ḥamâ (fig. 4; May 2012a: 222, pl. 8.16), queen's chalcedony seal (fig. 5; Radner 2008: 498 with fig. 12; 2012: 688 with fig. 1).

Bēl-Ḥarrān-bēlu-uṣur and that of the hardly known Mušēzib-Šamaš (Börker-Klähn 1982: 232 and fig. 2).

Besides the preserved images of queens, we know about more statues of Naqī'a: the golden statue erected at Kalḫu as well as others in Ḥarrān, which naturally did not survive.⁸⁹ Apparently, images of queens were not very rare, and they were definitely more common than those of officials. In light of what I explained above, can we accept the concept of Ornan that the scarcity of queens' images provides evidence of their insignificant political and religious role? Can we even continue to claim that the images of the Assyrian queens were scarce?

The imagery of the steles of Bēl-Ḥarrān-bēlu-uṣur and Mušēzib-Šamaš slavishly follows that of the royal steles, but the dignitaries represented on them lack any attributes at all. Their garments are identical to those of the officials on the royal palace reliefs. The disproportional figure of Mušēzib-Šamaš also displays clear signs of provincialism and a lack of artistic skill. The images of the queens, on the contrary, are adorned with richly elaborated gowns with shawls and with mural crowns. In the time of Sargonids, the mural crown was exclusively the headgear of queens.⁹⁰ The tokens that they hold in their hands were probably specially adapted from the Western monuments for the Sargonid queens. Libbāli-šarrat is represented as enthroned in an imitation of Mullissu, while the kings are always presented standing upright on their steles. It seems plausible that the queens' iconography was specially created in the time of Esarhaddon and Assurbanipal.⁹¹ Some of its elements, like the mirror and the flower, were borrowed from Western imagery. It is conceivable that these were used only in the imagery and not in reality. However, the queens' luxurious gowns and mural crowns were doubtlessly worn. The embroidered gowns, clad with gems and golden plaques, similarly to the gowns of the kings, were certainly part of the queens' attire before Sargon, as well as during his time, as proved by finds from the queens' tombs.⁹² The mural crown, which was probably the headgear of the king in the time of Assurnāširpal II,⁹³ was transformed into the crown of the queen, starting with Naqī'a at least. Queens' tombs display a variety of luxurious headdresses—including a tasseled headband, the symbol of royalty worn by kings, queens, crown princes, and probably even by Sargon's brother Sīn-aḫu-uṣur⁹⁴—but not a single mural crown has been found among them. Finally, the

89. SAA 13 61 and 188.

90. Mural crowns were probably adapted from the kings. Only one image of an Assyrian king wearing a mural crown is known. It is a representation on a glazed tile (Reade 1987: 140, fig. 1) probably from the reign of Assurnāširpal II (883–859 B.C.E.). Though the join between the fragment with the crown and the fragment with the beard is uncertain, the crowned figure is accompanied by an armor-bearer with the king's weaponry (a bow and quiver with arrows), and he has two daggers in his wide belt. These iconographical details identify with certainty that the figure in the mural crown is a king, although Börker-Klähn has claimed that it represents a queen as a "priestess" of Ištar (1997: 228–29). See also p. 266 n. 119 below. Note that mural crowns as the queens' headgear are attested only in the time of the Sargonids. See p. 271 n. 140 and p. 281 n. 192 in this regard.

91. In fact, the iconography of the royal steles and rock reliefs began to evolve already with Senacherib, departing from the traditional image of the king with the 'stretching the finger' (*ubāna tarāšu*) gesture. However, this is the subject for another essay.

92. E.g., Hussein and Suleiman 2000: pic. 36, IM 105966; Hussein 2016: 21–22, 94–95, pls. 77–78, 79a–b, 80c–e.

93. See n. 90 above. It is worth noting that in the Hellenistic period, both gods and goddesses were adorned with mural crowns (*passim*). In the Sassanian period, the mural crown was an attribute of the king (*passim*).

94. See May 2012a: 203–4 and 220–24 with figures 8.12a, b–8.18a, b and p. 272 with n. 143 below for a detailed discussion.

element of iconography of Mullissu—the enthroned representation—was adopted for Libbāli-šarrat. This is probably connected with Assurbanipal’s multiple similes to gods.⁹⁵ Thus, the king’s spouse was likened to the goddess by means of iconographic allusion.

Although “the Neo-Assyrian royal woman had no visual tradition of her own,”⁹⁶ it was carefully and purposely invented for her in the Sargonids’ time. In fact, we see the monumental imagery of the queens evolving from the traditional imageless stele of Sennacherib’s queen via the innovative attributes of Naqī’a to the most elaborate representations of Libbāli-šarrat.

5. Involvement of Royal Women in International Affairs and Matters of Succession

Some royal women were actively involved in Assyrian international affairs. Many of them gained their position through diplomatic marriages, which naturally opened access to the international sphere. The greatest Assyrian queens, Sammu-rāmat and Naqī’a, as well as the latter’s sister Abi-rāmu, had non-Assyrian, but West Semitic names, as did the less renowned queens Ḥamā, Iabā, and Ataliā.⁹⁷ From his inscriptions, we also know about Shalmaneser III’s marriages to the daughters of the most important Western kings.⁹⁸ The daughter of Sargon II, Aḥāt-abīša, was married to the king of Tabāl.⁹⁹

The first evidence of active involvement by a royal woman in international affairs comes from the inscription on the aforementioned boundary stone from Pazarḡik, installed jointly by Adad-nērārī III and Sammu-rāmat, which served as a border between the territories of Ušpilulume of Kummuḥi and Qalparuda, son of Palalam, king of the Gurgum.¹⁰⁰

Naqī’a was involved in Babylonian affairs, which has driven some scholars to suggest that she was of Babylonian origin and that she even ruled Babylonia in the name of her son.¹⁰¹ Although Babylonia was a vassal to Assyria during the reign of Esarhaddon, it was never actually a real Assyrian province,¹⁰² and a great deal of

95. Machinist 2006:166–67, 171; May 2007, part 1, ch. 2, and p. 274 with nn. 153–54 below.

96. Ornan 2002: 477.

97. Sammu-rāmat: See Novotny 2002: 1083–84. For a discussion of her name, see Weinfeld 1991. Naqī’a: See Streck 2001: 929. Abi-rāmu: See Mattila 1998: 12–14 s.v. Abi-rāmu 9 and introductory section. For the names of Naqī’a and her sister, see also Melville 1999: 13–16. Ḥamā: Hussein and Suleiman 2000: 399, pl. 183; al-Rawi 2008: 136, text no. 16. Iabā: See Frahm 2000: 485. For a discussion of the possible Judahite or Arabic origin of Iabā and Ataliā, see Dalley 1998 and 2008; Zadok 2008: 327–29; Frahm 2014: 184–88.

98. RIMA 3 A.0.102.2 1 40–41a, daughter of Mutallu of Gurgum; RIMA 3 A.0.102.2 ii 22–23a, daughter of Sangara of Carchemish; of Haiānu, the man of Bīt-Gabbāri (Sam’alla), RIMA 3 A.0.102.2 ii 26; of Arrāmu of Bīt-Agūsi (Unqi/Patina), RIMA 3 A.0.102.2 ii 28; of Katī of Quwē A.0.102.40 iii 7–8. These marriages are also portrayed in the representations on the bronze bands of the Balawat Gates (King 1915: pl. 34, band 6b, daughter of Sangara; pl. 26, band 5b, daughter of Arrāmu). See Svärd 2015: 128–30 for a review of foreign women taken to the Assyrian court, some with their dowries, from Adad-nērārī II through Assurbanipal and the discussion of their possible position.

99. SAA 1 31. See also Aro-Valjus and Nissinen 1998: 59.

100. RIMA 3 A.0.104.3 15–20.

101. Winckler 1901: 189; Lewy 1952: 274 and Dietrich 1970: 26. For the most recent discussion, see Svärd 2015: 57–58. The texts that testify to Naqī’a’s involvement in politics, cult, and even military affairs are SAA 10 154, SAA 10 348, SAA 18 10, SAA 18 85, RINAP 4 2008, and RINAP 4 2010.

102. J. A. Brinkman has stressed on many occasions (e.g., 1973: 90; 1984: 20–21) that Babylonia was a special case in the Assyrian system of territorial control: the Assyrian kings either ruled it them-

diplomacy was needed to navigate its Chaldean chieftains and local urban nobility.¹⁰³ It is worth noting that Sīn-aḥu-ušur, Sargon's brother and *sukkallu*, was similarly involved in Babylonian affairs; apparently he controlled Babylonian administration in the absence of the king.¹⁰⁴

Šerū'a-ēṭirat, daughter of Esarhadon and sister of Assurbanipal, is mentioned in CT 53 966: 9'–10' and rev. 2 together with Kandalānu, Assurbanipal's puppet king of Babylonia and Elam. The letter, though badly damaged, clearly deals with political matters.¹⁰⁵ The other, post-Assyrian piece of evidence for Šerū'a-ēṭirat's involvement in international affairs comes not from a cuneiform source but from a 3rd-century B.C.E. Aramaic tale of the war between Assurbanipal and Šamaš-šumu-ukīn.¹⁰⁶ It tells of the attempts by the princess Šerū'a-ēṭirat/Saritrah to make peace between her brothers, kings of Assyria and Babylonia, respectively. Despite its legendary character, the story reflects the influence that the kings' sister had.

The cases of involvement of the magnates in international affairs are in fact restricted to Šamši-ilu alone. These are the two aforementioned boundary stones from Antaqya and Mar'āš (Pazarḡik).¹⁰⁷ Šamši-ilu established the border between the territories of Zakkūru of Ḥamāt and Attār-šumkī, son of Abi-rāmu/Arrāmu of Bit-Agūsi. For Ušpilulume of Kummuḥi, Adad-nērārī III and Sammu-rāmat established their Pazarḡik stele. The inscription of Šamši-ilu is written on the back of their stele. In fact, this inscription, incised by Šamši-ilu in the name of Shalmaneser IV, confirms the border previously granted to Ušpilulume by Adad-nērārī III and Sammu-rāmat. There is no doubt that both of the boundary inscriptions of Antaqya and Mar'āš (Pazarḡik) were in fact incised by Šamši-ilu, although he explicitly did it in the name of Adad-nērārī III and Shalmaneser IV.

If Šamši-ilu, as suggested by Yukata Ikeda,¹⁰⁸ was indeed Bar-ga'jā, the king of KTK, he made the treaty with Matī'il, king of Arpad, son of the same Attār-šumkī, known from the Sefire Aramaic inscriptions. However, as has been shown by Andreas Fuchs, this is highly unlikely, and Bar-ga'jā was the minor king of an otherwise unknown kingdom of KTK in the West, which profited from the weakness of Assyria in this period.¹⁰⁹ The sphere of Šamši-ilu's interference in international relations is restricted to the states bordering his province.

Naqī'a/Zakūtu is the only person, aside from the king, known to have been involved in matters of succession. In addition to the Succession Treaties of Esarhadon, the queen-mother, the elder of the entire royal family,¹¹⁰ issued her own treaty. She made Assurbanipal's brothers, Šamaš-šumu-ukīn and Šamaš-mētu-uballit,

selves directly or installed puppet kings. Nonetheless, some of these so-called vassal kings such as Aššur-nādin-šumi, son of Sennacherib, or Šamaš-šumu-ukīn, brother of Assurbanipal, were from the royal family (May 2012a: 206; 2018: 521–22).

103. For the probable case of Babylonian nobility woman's involvement in international affairs, see the aforementioned letter of Barsipītu to Sargon (SAA 17 73) together with SAA 17 68. I agree with Svärd (2015: 139–41) that Barsipītu as the widow of the local chieftain acted as regent for her adolescent son.

104. May 2012a: 205–6; May 2018: 521–22.

105. Frame 1992: 195, 300–301.

106. Steiner and Nims 1985.

107. RIMA 3 A.0.104.2 4–11a and A.0.105.1 11–13a.

108. Ikeda 1999: 281–90.

109. See Fuchs 2008: 93 for the latest discussion and previous literature.

110. SAA 2 5. For Sammu-rāmat and Naqī'a as the heads of the royal household, see Svärd 2015: 41. For females as heads of households throughout Mesopotamian history, see p. 275 n. 160.

as well as all the royal offspring and family, together with all of the Assyrian elite, swear loyalty to Esarhaddon's crown prince, Assurbanipal.¹¹¹ We can speculate about Sammu-rāmat's or Šamši-ilu's involvement in the succession of Adad-nērārī III—as well as Šamši-ilu's influence on the accessions to the throne of Shalmaneser IV, Aššūr-dān III and Aššūr-nērārī V—but our sources are silent. Naqī'a was also apparently involved in Esarhaddon's accession.¹¹² The case of Queen-Mother Naqī'a/Zakūtu, who left documental evidence of installing her grandson on the throne, has no precedents or parallels in the entire history of Mesopotamia.

6. The Religious Role of Neo-Assyrian Royal Women

Joan Westenholz wrote, "Mesopotamian women are most visible functioning in the religious sphere."¹¹³ Aside from the king and predominantly male professional personnel, Neo-Assyrian royal women were probably the only ones who participated in the state cult. By the state cult, I mean here the cult of Aššur, the tutelary deity and namesake of the empire. As is well known, the Assyrian king was the chief priest of Aššur.¹¹⁴ It will be demonstrated that women of the royal family were involved in the state cult as well, but not the magnates. Notably, evidence for the crown prince's participation in the state rituals is limited to only one pictorial representation.¹¹⁵

There are three ritual texts that mention state officials. However, one of them is the triumph celebration, also known as the Assyrian War Ritual, dating to the time of Assurbanipal.¹¹⁶ The officials participate in it as military officers. Judging from the text and the representation of this ritual, not only officials but also the entire army joined in this media event, which was a spectacular performance aimed at a wide audience, including the inhabitants of the capital and those of Assyrian and subjugated cities. The purpose of this performance was to glorify the king. In the other two cases, the reading of the titles of magnates and their function in a ritual is uncertain.¹¹⁷

In comparison to the magnates, there is rather abundant evidence of the royal women as participants in the state cult.¹¹⁸ It has been suggested by many scholars, among them Julian Reade, Simo Parpola, Jutta Börker-Klähn, and Eckart Frahm,

111. SAA 2 8. See Melville 1999: 79–90 for a discussion.

112. This has been extensively treated in the research, but sources did not preserve any direct evidence on this matter. See, e.g., Melville 1999: 23 and elsewhere.

113. Westenholz 1990: 520. It should be stressed, however, that we know next to nothing about Neo-Assyrian priestesses.

114. See, e.g., Magen 1986: 65–92; Maul 1999.

115. On the reliefs of the passage leading to the Ištar Temple (fig. 6), the crown prince is shown strutting in front of the royal rickshaw.

116. K. 3438a + 9912, K. 9923, and K. 10209, the duplicates of the same ritual. See May 2012b, especially 464 with figs. 1, 1a, for the representations of these rituals. See Deller 1992: 341–44 and SAA 20 18 for the text edition.

117. Thus, Menzel 1981: T 44, A. 485 + 3109 = SAA 20 1 rev. 18 has ^{lu}GAR.KUR, which probably stands for *kurgarrū*, like in K. 3438a + 9912 9', because he deals with an attribute of Mullissu. ^{lu}GAL^{mes} participates with the king in the ritual for Aššur and Ištar, but the context is broken, and their role in this ritual is unclear (Menzel 1981: T 99, VAT 10112 = SAA 20 19 ii 5, 8).

118. The inscription on the aforementioned bronze relief representing Naqī'a describes the *mis pi* ritual in which she and the king participated. However, this ritual did not belong to the Assyrian state cult and took place in Babylon. Svärd has collected abundant evidence concerning Naqī'a's involvement in rituals (2015: 55), but none of it explicitly relates to the state cult. Svärd also discusses the evidence

that Assyrian queens were the earthly paragon of Aššur's spouse Mullissu, as the king was that of Aššur himself.¹¹⁹ The recent and very comprehensive discussion by Wiebke Meinhold presumes that this is the most plausible, though not unequivocal, possibility.¹²⁰

Pictorial evidence of the queen performing in the cult of Mullissu, apparently equated with Ištar of Nineveh, is found on seals and sealings. On the golden signet ring of Hamâ, the queen of Shalmaneser IV, she is represented worshipping an enthroned goddess, Mullissu/Ištar of Nineveh (fig. 4). On the chalcedony seal recently acquired by the British Museum (fig. 5) and on its sealings, all from Nineveh,¹²¹ both the king and the queen are shown worshipping the enthroned Mullissu. Sealings of a similar seal from the reign of Sargon II with the king and the queen adoring a deity standing on an animal were also found in Kalḫu.¹²² Karen Radner identifies both of these seals as the personal seals of the queen.¹²³

On a golden stele-shaped pendant unearthed at tomb III, coffin 1 in the queens' tombs at Kalḫu, a young female is represented standing in a supplication gesture before Ištar. Wearing her warrior attire, the goddess is depicted standing as well. The figure, appearance, and girded gown of the young worshiper are very similar to those of Queen Ḥamâ on her signet ring discovered in the same tomb, but in coffin 2. However, the poor quality of the photographs in both publications does not permit us to see further details.¹²⁴

As for textual evidence for the relationship of the queen to Mullissu,¹²⁵ Naqī'a dedicated jewelry to Mullissu/Bēlet-Nīnua for the stability of Esarhaddon's reign, as well as for their lives.¹²⁶ Three queens, which bear originally Assyrian names and were probably Assyrian themselves, had Mullissu and Ištar as theophoric

of Naqī'a providing for the temples but notes that these instances are not clear (ibid.). Moreover, Naqī'a actively participated in the religious matters of the entire Assyrian Empire (2015: 54).

As for the association of the queen with Išhara, the patron of matrimonial love (see Parpola 2012: 619 with n. 35), it is well-attested through the appearance of Išhara's symbol, the scorpion, on the queens' seals (Herbordt 1997, 279, 281–82; Radner 2008, 494–502; Radner 2012b: 690–93; Meinhold 2009: 242–43; Svärd 2015: 67–68 with n. 325). Nonetheless, so far nothing is known about the queens' involvement in the cult of Išhara (Svärd 2015: 74–75). Išhara was closely associated with Ištar of Assur since the Old Assyrian time and had a chapel in the temple of the latter (Meinhold 2009: 69–71). In the Neo-Assyrian texts, Išhara appears as *bēlet dadmē* 'the lady of settlements', which might have been connected with the mural crown of the queens. *Sebettu*, the Pleiades, are called "sons of Išhara." In Babylonian temple lists (the earliest of which come, however, from Assurbanipal's library) and in Neo-Babylonian administrative records, the name of her temple is É.ŠÁ.SUR.RA, meaning the 'House of Motherly Love'. See Prechel 1996: 148, 154, 157, 160–61 for text references.

119. Reade 1987: 143; Parpola 2012: 613–14, 619; Frahm 2014: 215. Börker-Klähn sees the queen as a *Vertreterin* of Ištar based on the iconography of Assurnasirpal II's(?) glazed brick (1997: 228–29 with pl. 13, fig. 4), which in my opinion represents the king.

120. Meinhold 2009: 240–45.

121. Radner 2008: 498–99 with figs. 9–10, 12–17. Impressions, Radner 2008: 498, figs. 10, 11.

122. Radner 2008: 497.

123. Radner 2008: 497–99; 2012b.

124. Hussein and Suleiman 2000: pic. 140. In this catalog, the description of the representation on the pendant is absolutely wrong. The museum and field number are missing. According to Hussein 2016: 134, this pendant is ND 373/IM 118091 from tomb III, coffin 1. The photograph appears at Hussein 2016: 103c. L. al-Gailani Werr also assumed that this might be the representation of a queen (al-Gailani Werr 2008: 156).

125. See Meinhold 2009: 240–94.

126. Deller 1983: 20–22; RINAP 4 2005–6.

elements: Mullissu-mukannišat-Nīnua, (Mullissu-ina)-Ešarra-ḥammāt, and (Ištar?-ina)-libbi-āli-šarrat.¹²⁷

The most important evidence is the outstanding ritual text BM 121206 presumably from Assur. Of a huge amulet-form tablet¹²⁸ which once contained 10 columns, only the reverse is preserved. The text was originally composed in the time of Sennacherib, but the tablet might be a later copy since the areas that were broken in the original are marked with ‘broken’ (*hepi*).¹²⁹ The text involves many gods, but its main divine protagonists are Aššur, Mullissu and Šerū’a.¹³⁰ The main human protagonists of the ritual are the king and royal women (not the queen only, but also the king’s daughter and sister). Of particular interest is the last paragraph (x 53’–57’):

⁵³[GIM *sal-q*]u ina IGI ⁴Še-ru-u-a ep-pu-lu ⁵⁴[DUMU.MUNU]S² MAN GIM MU-šá-ma ⁴Še-ru-u-a DUMU.MUNUS ⁵⁵AN.ŠAR ma-a ki-i ḥa-an-ni-u li-iz-mu-ru ⁵⁶la DU₁₀.GA a-ḥat LUGAL GIM MU-šá-ma ⁴Še-ru-u-a ⁵⁷DINGIR-te¹³¹ AN.ŠAR ma-a ki ḥa-ni-i li-iz-mu-ru DU₁₀.GA.

[When the boiled me]at is presented to Šerū’a, it is not good if [the daught]er of the king addresses her (with the words), “Šerū’a (is the) daughter of Aššur”—thus they shall sing.” But if the sister of the king addresses her (with the words), “Šerū’a (is the) goddess(?) of Aššur’ thus they shall sing”—this is good.

Earlier in this ritual (ix 56’), the king’s daughter is said to call out Šerū’a’s name. Association of a king’s daughter with this goddess may also be expressed in the names of Esarhaddon’s daughter and Assurbanipal’s sister Šerū’a-ētirat. Three astrological reports from three different scholars of Esarhaddon and Assurbanipal, two of them Babylonian, repeat word for word a prediction that the *entu*-priestess will become pregnant if Scorpius stands in a halo of the moon, obviously quoting the same source, apparently *Šumma Sin ina tāmartišu*.¹³² In the earlier periods, the office of the *entu*-priestess is associated with the king’s daughters. We know nothing about the connection of the *entu*-priestesses and the king’s daughters in Assyria,¹³³ but these reports should be also mentioned in conjunction with Esarhaddon’s

127. For the full names of the latter two, see Radner 1997: 406 and Ambos 2001: 660–61. See also Frahm 2014: 189–90 and Meinhold 2009: 240–45. W. Meinhold assumes that these could be their throne names. Tašmētu-šarrat probably married Sennacherib while he was still the crown prince and thus kept her name (Frahm 2014: 189 with n. 116). That might be not her birth name, but the one received after marriage to the crown prince. The connection between Nabû, Tašmētu, the Assyrian crown prince, and other royal offspring is clearly stated in SAA 10 30. See also Radner 2008: 502.

128. SAA 20 52; 190 × 243 × 26.5(+) mm.

129. BM 121206 6 3’–12’.

130. For a discussion of Šerū’a as a daughter and/or the wife of Aššur, see Meinhold 2009: 201–3 with further literature.

131. The collation of the tablet proves unequivocally that the first sign of line 57’ is intact (contra van Driel 1960: 102; Menzel 1981: T 68, and SAA 20 52). It is clearly DINGIR. There is no *al*, as suggested by W. Meinhold (2009: 216, n. 1302; 2014: 146 n. 32) and, following her, by E. Frahm (2014: 216 with n. 239). The second sign *te* is also intact and clear. I am grateful to J. Fincke for the detailed photographs she made for me in the British Museum and for her confirmation of the collation. For DINGIR/*il-ti*: ⁴Iš-tar in the commentary to The Babylonian Theodicy, see *BWL*: 76, commentary line 8 and the recent edition by E. Jiménez (2017).

132. SAA 8 147 rev. 2, 663/2 B.C.E., from Nabû-mušēši, SAA 8 307 1, from the Babylonian astrologer Zākīru, and SAA 8 480 7, from Nabû-aḥḥē-iddina of Dilbat.

133. All of the mentions of *entus* are restricted to lexical lists, the aforementioned reports (Macgregor 2012: 8–9), and debt records (SAA 14 68). See Svärd 2008: 84 for discussion. NIN.DINGIR.RA is restored as the apposition to DUMU.MÍ.LUGAL in SAA 8 104 11.

daughter, Šerū'a-ēṭirat, with her legendary fame,¹³⁴ since her literacy reminds us of the most famous *ēntu*-priestess in Mesopotamia, Enḫeduanna.¹³⁵

We know of at least one sister and one daughter of Sennacherib: Aḫāt-abīša and Šadditu, respectively. It is not impossible that the reliefs of the passage leading toward the Ištar Temple in the Southwest Palace of Sennacherib at Nineveh, which depict a royal ritual involving five female actors, represent a similar—if not the same—ritual as BM 121206, discussed above (fig. 6). The crown prince is also involved in this ritual. He is parading in front of the royal rickshaw. The attire and the headdress of the women on the reliefs are identical to those in the statue in the round (fig. 7, p. 270), which shows a woman in a gesture of supplication with folded hands. Both three-dimensional representations and this gesture of worship before the gods are reserved for royalty¹³⁶ in the Neo-Assyrian visual repertory. It is most plausible that those images—as well as three heads¹³⁷ (fig. 8a, b [p. 270] and Strommenger 1970: 30, pl. 20c [NnX1]), which is all that remains of probably similar statues—represented sisters and daughters of the king, though queens cannot be totally excluded. Two miniature female images found in Assur wear the same headgear (fig. 9, p. 272):¹³⁸ one of them is also draped in a shawl similar to that of Naqī'a on the bronze relief or Libbāli-šarrat on her stele or the Garden Scene. As we see again, royal women were not underrepresented in Assyrian art at all. It is worth noting here that the headdress of these female images closely reminds the circlets of the high priestesses (*ēntus*) of the Ur III and OB periods, who also were kings' daughters and thus sisters.¹³⁹

7. Royal and Divine Families

In conjunction with the religious role of the Neo-Assyrian queens, the parallelism between the family of Aššur and the royal family, already noticed by Simo Parpola (2012: 619–620), should be further stressed. However, the concept of a royal family as an image of the divine family—or vice versa, in fact—is not limited to queens only; it includes the triad of king, queen, and crown prince, found in this order for humans in the distribution lists of Sargon II (as, for instance, in SAA 1 34):

134. Steiner and Nims 1985.

135. SAA 16 28.

136. The only exception is the female statues discussed here. Statues of kings with folded hands were installed in the temples, apparently before the divine statues (Strommenger 1970: pls. 1, 4, 5, 6b, 7, 15c–d). Naturally, three-dimensional statues of the gods existed as well (e.g., Strommenger 1970: 8–14, 16d–e). Most of the divine statues were made of precious materials that did not survive to our days. There were also beardless statues in the round (Strommenger 1970: 17; Roobaert 1996: figs. 1–4). Both were subject to severe iconoclasm, especially the latter, which apparently represented Šamšī-ilu (Strommenger 1970; Fuchs 2008: 96–98). Note, however, that Neo-Assyrian officials are often represented adorning the king with folded hands (May 2007: part 1, ch. 2).

137. E. Strommenger (1970: 28–29) suggested the time of Sargon II or later. Andrae 1935: 108, “spätassyrisches” for the head from Assur (fig. 8b).

138. Andrae 1935: 108, pl. 48 m, n.

139. For the circlets of *ēntu*-priestesses, see Suter 2008. Compare also to the *kudurru* of Meli-Šipak with the grant to his daughter Ḫunubat-Nanāia (Paulus 2014: 390–401). However, the women attending the royal couple in the Garden Scene also wear circlets. Among headgear from the queens' tombs, the golden crown found with the upper skeleton in the tomb of Iabā and Atalia (tomb II; Hussein 2016: 69, pl. 37a) is closest in form to the circlet.

Figure 6. Reliefs of the passage leading toward the Ištar Temple; Southwest Palace of Sennacherib at Nineveh. Drawing copyright of the Trustees of the British Museum. Photograph by N. N. May.

Figure 8 a, b (above). Heads of the statues of women (from Assur and Nineveh). a. Copyright of the Trustees of the British Museum. b. After Andrae 1935: 48a.

Figure 7 (left). Statue of a woman in a gesture of supplication with folded hands.

Rev

2' [x] GÚ.UN KUG.UD 40 MA.NA KUG.UD *ku-um* z[Ú-A]M¹.[SI]
 3' 20 ^{túg}GADA^{meš} [2]0 ^{túg}šad-din 3 DUG.LA *ma-qar-te*
 4' 10 [l]a-at-[tú K]U₆ 1-lim KU₆^{meš} PAP *ma-da-tú*
 5' 1 GIL KUG.GI 20 *kap-pi* KUG.UD 10 ^{túg}GADA^{meš} 10 ^{túg}šad-din
 6' 4 ^{túg}šad-din š[a n]a-me-di 1 DUG.LA *ma-qar-te* KU₆
 7' PAP *na-mur-tú* PAP *an-ni-ú ša* É.GAL
 8' 5' MA.NA KUG.UD 5 ^{túg}šad-din 5 ^{túg}GADA^{meš} 1 DUG.LA *ma-[qar-te* KU₆]
 9' 1 *la-at-tú* KU₆ 1-lim KU₆^{meš} PAP *ma-da-te* MÍ.É.[GAL]
 10' 10 MA.NA KUG.UD 5 ^{túg}šad-din 5 ^{túg}GADA^{meš} 1 DUG.LA [*ma-qar-te* KU₆]
 11' 1 *la-at-tú* KU₆ 1-me KU₆^{meš} PAP *ma-da-te* DUMU.LUGAL

[. . .] talents of silver, 40 minas of silver in place of i[vory], 20 tunics, 20 togas, 3 potfuls of iced (fish), creels of 1,000 fish all tribute; one crown of gold,¹⁴⁰ 20 silver bowls, 10 tunics, 10 togas, 4 togas *made to measure*, one potful of iced fish; all audience gift: all this to the Palace; 5 minas of silver, 5 togas, 5 tunics, one potful of ic[ed fish], 1 creel of 100 fish all tribute: the queen; 10 minas of silver, 5 togas, 5 tunics, one potful of [iced fish], 1 creel of 100 fish; all tribute: the crown prince

Or SAA 7 155 (list of banquet meal distribution [?]):

1. 2²-te² BUR¹ ṛša¹ É¹. [GAL²] second meal of the palace
2. 1 MÍ.É?. [GAL²] 1, the queen
3. [1] DUMU.LUGAL 1, the crown prince

Interestingly, the triad of the king, queen, and crown prince is present through their sealings, which appear together on a bulla of a folded papyrus.¹⁴¹

The divine family Aššur, Mullissu, Ninurta/Adad is attested in this order in rituals¹⁴² and on the Maltaï relief (fig. 10, p. 277). It is obvious that the queen's position was superior to that of the crown prince, and her role in the state cult was probably one of the reasons for this. Moreover, Libbāli-šarrat is represented enthroned, as is Mullissu/Ištar (figs. 1 and 3 for the queen and 4, 5, and 10 for the goddess).

140. SAA 1 34 translates GIL here as 'mural crown'. It is worth noting that, in Sargon II's reliefs (and only there), we find tributaries presenting to the king models of fortresses, presumably of their cities, as a gesture of subjugation (see SAA 1 34, fig. 12, illustrating this text, particularly the upper register where two tributaries are depicted delivering the fortresses models). Many similar representations appear on the reliefs of façade n and rooms 6 and 10 of the Ḫorsābād palace (Botta and Flandin 1848: pls. 36, 106, 125–27, 129–30, 133–34; Albenda 1986: pls. 1, 24, 27–30, 32–33, 68). The caption of SAA 1 fig. 12 by J. Reade suggests that "those above are westerns, with goods including models of walled cities, or mural crowns, which presumably symbolize sovereignty over the cities represented." This interpretation seems most plausible to me, but the conjunction *or* is not necessary. The small fortresses in the hands of the tributaries can be in fact *both* the models of their cities *and* mural crowns, because the models made of precious metal could serve as jewelry. This is supported by the fact that, in the same relief in room 6, which depicts the tributaries with walled fortresses, tributaries also appear with jewelry (Botta and Flandin 1948: pls. 104–6; Albenda 1986: 66–67). The interpretation of *kilīlu* (GIL) as *mural* crown and not just a crown is more problematic, however, and it depends heavily on cultural context and pictorial evidence.

141. BM 84751. Radner 2008: 500, fig. 18. However, the sealings of the kings and the crown prince, which appear together, are much more numerous (Radner 2008: 505–6, figs. 23–30).

142. In BM 121206, Šerū'a is inserted after Mullissu. See also Menzel 1981: T 112, A.485 + 3109 10'.

There is also a status signifier common to the king, the queen, and the crown prince. This is the tasseled headband, worn by the king above his turban. The crown prince is wearing the tasseled headband only. For Šamaš-šumu-ukīn as the crown prince of Babylonia, a special zig-zagged tasseled headband was invented. He is represented wearing it on the Sam'alla stele of Esarhaddon, where it distinguishes him from Assurbanipal, who is adorned with the traditional Assyrian headband. Queens are thrice represented wearing this headgear: Ḫamā is decorated with it on her signet ring (fig. 4), while the queen on the chalcidony seal and Naqī'a on the aforementioned bronze relief have it together with the mural crown (fig. 5 and May 2012a: fig. 8.17). A tasseled headband, which belonged to Iabā or Atalia, was found in their tomb (tomb II).¹⁴³

Figure 9. Depiction of a female worshiper on the fragment of a glazed jar. After Andrae1935: 48m.

8. Most Important Features of the Queens' Representations

We have seen that the royal women were not underrepresented. Now we should move to the next question and ask: how were they represented? Joan Scott has quoted Gladston speaking on the distinction between sex and gender: “Athene has nothing of sex except the gender, nothing of the woman except the form.”¹⁴⁴ Below I will analyze the representation of sex and gender in the textual and pictorial descriptions of Assyrian royal women.

143. For a detailed discussion, see May 2012a: 203–4 with figs. 8.13–17. The same tasseled headband was carved, but then remodeled on the relief, which originally represented Sīn-aḫu-ušur, Sargon II's brother (May 2012a: 203–4 with fig. 8.12).

144. Scott 1986: 1053.

Let us start with Sammu-rāmat and her famous Pazarḡik stele (RIMA 3 A.0.104.3):

¹*ta-ḥu-mu šá* ^m10—ÉRIN.TÁḤ MAN KUR Aš-šur ²A ^mŠam-ši—10 MAN KUR Aš-šur ³fŠa-am-mu-ra-mat MUNUS.É.GAL ⁴šá Šam-ši—10 MAN KUR Aš-šur ⁵AMA ^m10—ÉRIN.TÁḤ MAN KAL MAN KUR Aš-šur ⁶kal-lat ^mdŠul-ma-nu—MAŠ ⁷MAN kib-<rat> 4-ti ina u₄-me ^mUš-pi-lu-lu-me ⁸MAN ^{uru}Ku-mu-ha-a-a-na ^m10—ÉRIN.TÁḤ MAN KUR Aš-šur ⁹fŠa-am-mu-ra-mat MUNUS.É.GAL ¹⁰idPu-rat-tú ú-še-bi-ru-u-ni ¹¹mA-tar-šum-ki A ^mAD-ra-a-me ^{uru}Ar-pa-da-a-a ¹²a-di 8 MAN^{mes}-ni šá KI-šú ina ^{uru}Pa-qi-ra-ḥu-bu-na ¹³si-dir-ta-šú-nu KI-šú-nu am-daš-iš uš-ma-na(?)—šú-nu ¹⁴e-kim*-šú-nu-ti a-na su-zu-ub ZI^{mes}-šú-nu ¹⁵e-li-ú

(1–7a) Boundary stone of Adad-nērārī, king of Assyria, son of Šamšī-Adad (V), king of Assyria, (and of) Sammu-rāmat, the palace-woman of Šamšī-Adad, king of Assyria, mother of Adad-nērārī, strong king, king of Assyria, daughter-in-law of Shalmaneser (III), king of the four quarters. (7b–10) When Uspilulume, king of the Kummuhites, caused Adad-nērārī, king of Assyria, (and) Sammu-rāmat, the palace-woman, to cross the Euphrates, (11–15a) I fought a pitched battle with them—with Attār-šumkī, son of Abi-rāmu, of the city of Arpad, together with eight kings who were with him at the city Paqaraḥubunu. I took away from them their camp. To save their lives they dispersed.

It is usually assumed that the one who leads the battle is the king, though grammatically it can be the queen as well. In any case, she crosses the Euphrates, which is a heroic deed of warrior-kings,¹⁴⁵ and thus she is praised as a warrior.

Sargonid queens had their own military detachments (*kišru* and others) and other military stuff.¹⁴⁶ The first attestation of military units belonging to the queen seems to date to Sargon's queen. A new date for SAA 19 158 is suggested by Mikko Luukko's new reconstruction and translation of the letter. He convincingly argues that the letter to Sargon is from Sennacherib, who sent "10 chariot ow[ne]rs from the household of the queen."¹⁴⁷ Naqī'a is briefed on the military situation on the Elamite border even including very specific details.¹⁴⁸ Together with the inscription of Sammu-rāmat, this proves that at least in certain situations the queen-mothers at least were involved in military operations. The praise of Sammu-rāmat as a war-heroine and the military detachments of the Sargonid queens may be associated with the military aspect of Mullissu¹⁴⁹ and Ištar, similarly to the king representing the warrior-god Aššur.

In terms of the magnates, especially the *turtānus*, war was one of their main obligations. It is well known from the nonroyal sources that they waged campaigns, which royal inscriptions ascribe to the king.¹⁵⁰ When they could, the magnates

145. Compare Assurnaširpal II, RIMA 2 A.0.101.1 iii 33–34.

146. Note that on the chalcedony seal and its impressions (fig. 5), the cone of the headgear worn by the queen under the mural crown is protruding above it exactly like the same cone is protruding above the royal turban. In my opinion, this cone is the pointed termination of an Assyrian helmet.

147. SAA 19 158: 13–14a: 10 ^ria¹E[N¹] ^giš^rGIGIR¹meš¹ TA* É MUNUS.É.GAL¹. See also Parpola 2012: 626 for the military staff of the queen. K. Radner even states that both the queen and the crown prince had their own standing armies (2012: 692–93). See Svārd 2015b: 163 for a discussion.

148. SAA 18 85.

149. For the association of Mullissu with a weapon, see the coronation ritual from the time of Tukultī-Ninurta I: *a-ga-a ša Aš-šur u* ^giš⁸TUKUL^{mes} ša ^dNIN.LİL 'the crown of Aššur and the weapon of Mullissu' (Müller 1937: 10–11, KAR 135 + ii 15).

150. The *turtānu* conquered Ashdod for Sargon (Isa 20:1). The Eponym Chronicle tells that the *sukkallu* (Sīn-aḥu-ušur) destroyed Dūr-Iakin (Millard 1994: 48, B6 rev. 3–5; May 2012a: 205; 2018: 509)

boasted of their military achievements, and sometimes the king even gave them credit in the royal inscriptions.¹⁵¹ However, the magnates existed for going to war.¹⁵² Whoever led the company, the victory belonged to the king.

Moving on to Naqī'a, the characteristic she is often glorified for in the letters addressed to her and to the king is her wisdom. For instance, in SAA 10 244: 5a–9 the court exorcist (Marduk-šakin-šumi?), reporting that he was working with his colleagues to carry out the king's orders, remarks: *is-sa-he'-i-š [n]i-im-ma-al-lik [n]i-qab-bi* MÍ.AMA LUGAL [k]i'-i A-da-pi [t]a'-la'-i 'we shall take counsel together (and then) speak out—the mother of the king is as able as (the sage) Adapa!' Wisdom is another quality that distinguishes the kings and is ascribed to them in a number of royal inscriptions, in Assurbanipal's Coronation Hymn,¹⁵³ and in the text called now The Creation of the King. In the latter two, the king is called *māliku amēlu* 'an adviser/counsellor man'.¹⁵⁴ Already the Epic of Tukultī-Ninurta I calls him "he, who hears what people say/the voice of the people, the 'Counsel' of the land."¹⁵⁵ Adad-nērārī II's inscription says that when the gods created him, they "filled my lordly body with wisdom."¹⁵⁶ Sennacherib claims that his conception was watched by Bēlet-ilī, while "Nišiku (Ea) gave broad knowledge, the equal to (that of) wise Adapa, granted wide understanding."¹⁵⁷ This king himself is likened to the legendary sage by an unknown author.¹⁵⁸

It is not surprising that the queen-mothers are endowed with the male qualities appropriate to the kings. In the same letter SAA 10 244, Naqī'a is twice called

in 704 B.C.E. the magnates waged the campaign alone, probably revenging the death of Sargon without Sennacherib, who was mourning his father (Millard 1994: 49, B6 rev. 12).

151. Shalmaneser III sent his *turtānu* Daiān-Aššūr to wage the campaigns of his 27th, 28th, 30th, and 31st regnal years to the west, north, and northeast (Patina, Urarṭu, Parsua, etc.), while the king stayed at Kalḫu (RIMA 3 A.0.102.14 141b–156a, 159b–90; RIMA 3 A.0.102.16 228'–44', 268'–86'a, 291'–341'a). In his 29th year, Shalmaneser also sent his army to campaign without the king (RIMA 3 A.0.102.14 156b–59a; RIMA 3 A.0.102.16 286'b–90'). Only the *turtānu* Šamši-ilu dared to write about leading military campaigns of his own (the campaign to Damascus [Pazarḡik, RIMA 3 A.0.105.1 11–13a]; the campaign against Arḡištu (I), king of Urarṭu, reported in Šamši-ilu's lions' inscription, which also mentions his previous campaign to the west [RIMA 3 A.0.104.2010, 8b–18], and A.0.104. 2011). Šamši-ilu never says that he acts on the king's command. In his lions' inscription, he is even so bold to claim that he was sent to the campaign by the god Aššur.

152. See Mattila 2000: 149–57 on the magnates and their military activities, and especially p. 150 for the military troops of the magnates.

153. SAA 3 11 rev. 16.

154. Mayer 1987: 56, VAT 17019 rev. 31', 33'/ 36': *Be-let—DINGIR^{mes} . . . pi-it-'ql'-ma LUGAL ma-li-ku, a-me-lu/ Be-let—DINGIR^{mes} ip-ta-it-iq LUGAL ma-li-ku LÚ* 'Bēlet-ilī, create the king, advisor of a man/Bēlet-ilī created the king, advisor of a man'. See Jiménez 2013: 238 for the duplicate of this text, STT 24 5', and Jiménez 2013: 240–41 for the comment with the exhaustive overview of all interpretations of these lines. See also May 2007: part 1, ch. 2. For dating the composition of The Creation of the King to the Sargonid period or even to the time of Sargon II, see Jiménez 2013: 242–44. Assurbanipal's Coronation Hymn, SAA 3 11 rev. 16 has: "Aš-šur—DŪ—A LUGAL ma-li-ku a-me-lu 'Assurbanipal, the king, the advisor man'. The epithet *māliku amēlu* actually combines the Mesopotamian concept of wisdom as the ability to hear and listen with *māliku amēlu* 'an adviser/counselor man', especially in the light of the possibility that *mīlik* can be Assyrian vowel harmony for *mālik*. See Lambert 1957: 50 n.10.

155. Machinist 2006: 161, 18': *še-mu-u pi-i UN^{mes} mi-lik* KUR.

156. RIMA 1 A.0.99.2: 7: *zu-mur EN-ti-ia iš-pu-uk 'ta'-ši-im-'ta'*.

157. *Nin-ši-kù id-di-na kar-šu rit-pa-šú šin-na-at ABGAL A-da-pà iš-ru-ka pal-ka-a ḥa-sis-su* (RINAP 3/2 43 3–4a, paralleled by RINAP 3/2 42 25b–26). Note that Akkadian *palkā ḥasissu* here is the translation of Sumerian *geštug da gal*. The phraseology is standard from Tiglath-pileser III until Assurbanipal (CAD P s.v. *palkū* b).

158. SAA 10 380 3–4.

bēli. The application of masculine grammatical gender is typical in conjunction with high-ranking women in the Neo-Assyrian dialect.¹⁵⁹ In Mesopotamia in general, women of status could act as *pater familias*, and throughout various periods their names were often written with the male determinative.¹⁶⁰

The only queen who seems to be extolled for a “female quality” is the spouse of Sennacherib, Tašmētu-šarrat. The king describes her in his inscription: ^{ft}*Taš-me-tum-šar-rat*¹ MUNUS.É.GAL *hi-ir-tu na-ram-ti-ia ša* ^d*Be-let*—DINGIR^{mes} UGU *gi-mir* MUNUS^{mes} *ú-šak-li-la nab-ni-sa* ‘Tašmētu-šarrat, the palace-lady, my beloved spouse, whose form the goddess Bēlet-ilī made more perfect than (that of) all (other) women’.¹⁶¹ This line and a half is so tricky that it misled even such an infallible authority as Rykle Borger.¹⁶² First of all, it includes the term *hīrtu*, which means not just ‘wife’ but ‘equal status wife’.¹⁶³ Here it is written syllabically, but the Sumero-gram for *hīrtu* is MUNUS.NITA.DAM, which literally should be translated ‘androgynous spouse’¹⁶⁴ but in fact expresses the equality of a woman to her husband by means of representing her as a male. The term *hīrtu* conveys the same idea as putting both masculine and feminine determinatives before a female name.¹⁶⁵ Moreover, this case of *hīrtu* applied in the Neo-Assyrian period to a mortal woman, even if a queen, is a *hapax*, but it regularly appears in the expressions *hīrtu namaddu* and *hīrtu naramtu* as an epithet of goddesses, and primarily of Mullissu as a spouse of Aššur, starting with Tiglath-pileser I.¹⁶⁶

Beauty was not a primarily female quality in the ancient Near East, at least not when it came to royalty. The kings were praised for it much more often than the queens with the same and even more flowery expressions, as was Tašmētu-šarrat, “whose form the goddess Bēlet-ilī made more perfect than (that of) all women.”¹⁶⁷ In The Creation of Man and the Creation of the King, Ea thus instructs Belet-ilī to make a king of an ideal appearance: “Wrap with goodness his entire appearance, make his looks perfect, beautify his body.”¹⁶⁸ Besides the perfect appearance achieved during his creation, good looks are the gift of Bēlet-ilī in the list of gifts the king is endowed with by the gods.¹⁶⁹ In the annals of Adad-nārārī II the king’s perfect form is emphasized by the triple repetition: “The great gods . . . Adad-nārārī, attentive prince, duly they created me, made my appearance perfect (A. Kirk Grayson in RIMA 2: “they properly created me”), they altered my stature to lordly stature,

159. See Luukko 2004: 185; Svärd 2015, 83–84.

160. For the king’s daughters in the beginning of the 3rd to the beginning of the 2nd millennia B.C.E., see Lion 2009b; for Nuzi and Emar, see Grosz 1987, especially pp. 81–83 for a review of the sources; Lion 2009a; Abrahami 2011, especially for double “mf” determinatives before female names. See Brinkman 2007 for the Middle Babylonian and Wunsch 2006 for the Neo-Babylonian evidence.

161. RINAP 3/2 40 45’–46”a.

162. Borger 1988: 5.

163. CAD H s.v. *hīrtu*.

164. The ideogram MUNUS means ‘woman/female’, NITA ‘man/male’, and DAM ‘wife’.

165. See above, n. 160.

166. RIMA 2 A.0.87.1 iv 34–35. In documents, *hīrtu* is applied to humans only in the Old Babylonian period (CAD H s.v. *hīrtu* c [a]).

167. See above, RINAP 3/2 40 45”.

168. Mayer 1987: 56–57, rev. 34’–35’: *ṭa-a-bi ub-[b]i-ḫi gi-[mi]r la-ni-šú šu-ub-bi-i zi-i-mi-šú bu-un-ni-i zu-mur-šú*

169. Mayer 1987: 56–57, rev. 40’: *Be-let*—DINGIR^{mes} *it-ta-din bu-un-[na-an-ni-šú]* ‘Bēlet-ilī gave him his appearance’.

they rightly made perfect my features.”¹⁷⁰ Moreover, Assyrian high-ranking males are represented as richly adorned with jewelry.¹⁷¹

Beauty and perfection are among the most important features of the deities, being inherent in the appearance of gods as opposed to imperfect humans. The royal couple thus appears again as the earthly representatives of the divine couple of Aššur and Mullissu. What Borger saw as evidence of Sennacherib’s affection for his young wife turns out to be a rigid and quite banal rhetoric of Assyrian royal inscriptions, the routine of which is slightly broken by a mention of *absasātu* (female sphinxes) and *bēt ru’āmu*.¹⁷² It should be stressed that fertility, which was supposed to be the main virtue of the queens and which is so often praised in royal males, is never even mentioned in conjunction with royal females. Neither are they depicted with their children.

As for the images of royal females in Neo-Assyrian art, they distinctly lack signifiers of charm and sexuality. Breasts are flat, hair is short,¹⁷³ and, of course, there is no hint of nudity. If not for their headgear and attire, the representations on the reliefs could be mistaken for those of eunuchs (fig. 6). As for the statues, they do display perennial Middle Eastern signifiers of beauty, such as moonlike roundness of face and conjunct brows. However, the male faces of the kings demonstrate the same “ideal” features of perfect royal image and are distinguished from females primarily by their beards. In pictorial representations of royal women, the stress is not on their femininity but on their perfection and dignity; in written sources, it is on their masculinity, however paradoxical it may sound. It was the femininity of the royal females and not the royal females themselves, which was underrepresented in Assyrian written and pictorial sources. In the case of royal women, the purpose was to create a model image which reflected the ideology of the ruling gender, not an ideal image of a female. Like Athene, or her Mesopotamian precursor Ištar as the warrior-goddess, the images of Assyrian royal women lack femininity and sexuality.

170. RIMA 2 A.99.2: 5–6: [DI]NGIR ^rmeš GAL^{meš} . . . m10—ÉRIN.TÁH... *ki-niš ib-nu-ni* [. . .] ‘*nab-ni-te’ a-na nab-ni-ti EN-ti uš-te-en₆-nu-ú ši-’kín bu-na-n’-ia i-še-riš ú-šék-li-lu-ma*.

171. *Passim* on the reliefs. Note also the rich present of Sennacherib to Esarhaddon, which consisted of jewelry pieces such as bracelets, armllets, a headband and a necklace. The gift was apparently given on the occasion of the appointment of Esarhaddon as a crown prince, since in the same document he is endowed with the new name (SAA 12 88).

172. The word *ru’āmu* certainly has a connotation of sexual charm but is most often applied to goddesses (CAD R s.v. *ru’āmu* 1). Grayson and Novotny (2014: 42) translate *bīt ru’āme hidāti u rišāti* as ‘a palatial hall for lovemaking, happiness, and exultation’, while Borger’s (1988) translation for *bīt ru’āme* is ‘Palast der Liebe’. Note that in texts of Assurbanipal, similar—though not exactly the same—expressions are used to describe the bedchambers of divine couples (Borger with Fuchs 1996: 124 Sm 2101 i (55, 56); 139, T 150 TTafI i 22’ C i 46; 271 ii T 47). Thus, through applying this term to the queen’s quarters, Sennacherib is again employing the parallel between divine and royal couples. D. Ker-tai (2013: 117) claims that the layout of and archaeological evidence from the suite built by Sennacherib for Tašmētu-šarrat prove that it was the queen’s office rather than a “palace for lovemaking.” Female sphinxes can be a part of the queen’s entourage, as were her female servants, but they are irrelevant for understanding this part of the palace as a place of “lovemaking.”

173. Regardless of whether breasts were perceived in Assyria as sexy or not, although the observation of M. Cifarelli proves that they were (Cifarelli 1997: 221–22 with n. 71), one would expect them to be shown on representations of females as secondary sex characteristics. But they are not. The impression is that in Assyrian art, which is usually very meticulous in terms of details, female breasts are not indicated on purpose, in order not to draw the spectator’s attention to them. For hair as an attribute of female beauty, see, e.g., Gansell 2014: 403.

Figure 10. Sennacherib's Maltai relief. After Place 1867, vol. 3: pl. 45.

Both in written and pictorial sources, royal women are represented and referred to as male, not as female.

9. *Posthumous Fame: Tales of Assyrian Royal Women*

Unlike Sammu-rāmat and Naqīʾa, Tašmētu-šarrat did not leave an inscription of her own. The building inscription that praises her was written by Sennacherib. This actually emphasizes how powerful were Sammu-rāmat and Naqīʾa, whose interference in international and successional affairs is evidenced by documents that they issued themselves.¹⁷⁴

Is there anything that indicates the attitude to and evaluation of the royal females and their power by the contemporaries? Apparently there was a popular tradition beyond the cuneiform sources—probably Aramaic, oral, or both—that reflected the fame of Assyrian royal women. It survives as tales written in Aramaic or told by Greco-Roman authors. It is particularly relevant to the above discussion, because it reveals the visibility of Assyrian royal women and transmits some features also found in cuneiform sources.

Reade has already noted the legendary fame of Sammu-rāmat/Semiramis, which survived in Greek and rabbinic sources.¹⁷⁵ We can add the mentioning of Naqīʾa/Nitocris(?) by Herodotus¹⁷⁶ and the role of Šerūʾa-ēṭirat/Saritrah in the Aramaic tale of the war between Assurbanipal and Šamaš-šumu-ukīn. Legends are indeed indicative, providing evidence of both fame and esteem. The legendary evidence about Assyrian royal women is comparable to evidence about the kings. Moreover, it also contains the positive characteristics of the first royal women. Indeed, of all the mighty Assyrian kings¹⁷⁷ the Aramaic tales of Aḥiqar, in which the king is not the main protagonist, preserved the fame of Sennacherib.¹⁷⁸ Sardanapal is mentioned in Classical sources as a token of unable and vicious ruler, an effeminate king, spending time with his concubines.¹⁷⁹ Sardanapal and Assurbanipal have nothing in common but the name. Assurbanipal/Sarbanapal and Šamaš-šumu-ukīn/Sarmuge

174. To compare, we know about the might of the sultans' consorts and queen-mothers during the Sultanate of Women from narrative sources, created either by Ottoman historians or by foreign diplomats. These mighty women "ruled the world," but they did not issue international treaties of firmans. Those were signed by men, in spite of the fact that the Ottoman Empire in this period was ruled by women. See, e.g., Zilfi 1997; Goffman 2002.

175. Reade 1987: 139. For Semiramis, see Weinfeld and Dalley 2005 and Dalley 2013: 4, 26, 32, 98–99, 107, 120–21, 123–26. Classical sources for Semiramis are Herodotus (Hdt. 1 184), Ctesias apud Diodorus Siculus (D. S. ii 3–20, iii 1, 3); Strabo (Str. 2 i 27, 31 = C 81, 84; 11 xiv 8 = C 529; 12 ii 7 = C 357; 1 iii 559), Pompeius Trogus apud Justinus (Iust. i.1–2), and Quintius Curtius Rufus (Curt. 5, 4, 24; 7, 6, 20; 9, 6, 15, 23). Rabbinic sources are Lev. Rab. 19:16 and Esth. Rab. 3:2. Moreover, the fame of Sammu-rāmat is echoed also in the Armenian story of Ara the Beautiful (see Russell 1983) and commemorated on the reliefs of Aphrodisias on the Meander (Dalley 2013: 126, figs. 37–38).

176. Hdt. 1 185–88. See, e.g., Lewy 1952; Röllig 1969; Dalley 2013: 107, 120.

177. Naturally, Berossus wrote on a number of Assyrian kings and even their sons. But he cannot be counted as part of a popular tradition because he obviously based his work on the cuneiform sources. Together with many mistakes, his account provides a number of precise details (Burstein 1978: 23–26, 1–6b).

178. Holm 2014: 295–313. Later Christian Aramaic legends of Sennacherib (Holm 2014: 313–23) are of no relevance for us here, as they are obviously late and created under the impact of 2 Kgs 19 = Isa 36. The same is true for all of the Classical sources on Sennacherib besides Herodotus. Herodotus (Hdt. 2 241) describes the "Egyptian" campaign of Sennacherib, probably ascribing to that the events of Esarhaddon's reign.

179. E.g., Pomp. Trog. apud Iust. i, 3; D.S. ii. 23–27.

appear in the same early third-century B.C.E. Aramaic tale together with their sister Šerū'a-ēṭirat/Saritrah, but the real heroine of the tale is the princess, whose wisdom and diplomatic qualities gain her the main role in this story.¹⁸⁰

Greek—and, following them, Latin—authors did not distinguish between the deeds of the two famous Assyrian queens Sammu-rāmat and Naqī'a and credited both Semiramis and Nitocris with the embellishing and even founding of Babylon.¹⁸¹ Nonetheless, the evidence of G. Pompeus Trogus quoted by Justin has details that indeed preserved the perception of royal females as males, which is strikingly close to what we know from the Assyrian sources:

Ninus himself died, leaving a son called Ninyas, still a minor, and a wife, whose name was Semiramis. Semiramis, not daring to entrust the government to a youth, or openly to take it upon herself (as so many great nations would scarcely submit to one man, much less to a woman), pretended that she was the son of Ninus instead of his wife, a male instead of a female. [. . .] Having thus dissembled her sex at the commencement of her reign, she was believed to be a male.¹⁸²

It was often suggested that Sammu-rāmat was a regent when Adad-nērārī III was a minor¹⁸³ or even ruled in his stead while she was alive.¹⁸⁴ The most important is Trogus's (albeit very late) evidence that Semiramis pretended to be a male and was believed to be such. This may convey the Mesopotamian attitude of regarding women of status as males.¹⁸⁵

10. Conclusion

Regarding the visibility of women, a different methodological approach should be applied to the written and pictorial sources. I always stress that both should be

180. Steiner and Nims 1985.

181. Classical sources are quite accurate in rendering the name of Sammu-rāmat, unlike that of Naqī'a's (Weinfeld 1991). Particularly, the heroic deeds of Semiramis may echo the military fame of the "warrior-queen" Sammu-rāmat, and the tales of founding and embellishing Babylon probably mirror the involvement of Naqī'a in Esarhaddon's restoration of Babylon. Herodotus tells about Nitocris refurbishing Babylon (Hdt. 1 185–86), while the other authors based on tradition going back to Ctesias credit Semiramis with founding it (D.S. 7–9, Str. 2 1 31; Iust. i.2.7; Curt. 5, 4, 24). See Dalley 2013: 107, 120, 123–24. Obviously, Herodotus's narration is closer to the actual events than the others. Classical sources confuse Assyria and Babylonia on a regular basis (e.g., the same Herodotus, or Jdt 1:1, 7 and *passim*). Nonetheless, despite crediting Semiramis with founding Babylon (D.S. ii, 7–9), Diodorus Siculus clearly calls her an Assyrian queen. Diodorus Siculus (ii, 13–14, 16–20) describes the military undertakings of Semiramis, which may be an echo of the "military fame" of Sammu-rāmat. His description of Semiramis's construction of the temple of Bēl and furnishing it with the divine statues and the cultic utensils (D.S. ii, 9.4–9) might well reflect Esarhaddon's restoration of Esagila, in which Naqī'a actively participated (SAA 10 348, RINAP 4 2008, 2010, and probably SAA 10 154 and SAA 18 10).

182. 10 . . . *et ipse decessit, relicto adhuc inpubere filio Ninya et uxore Samiramide. 2,1 Haec neque inmaturo puero ausa tradere imperium nec ipsa palam tractare—tot ac tantis gentibus uix patienter uni uiro, nedum feminae parituris—simulat se pro uxore Nini filium, pro femina puerum. . . . 4 Sic primis initiis sexum mentita puer esse credita est.* Just. i. 1: 10–2. 2, 4. Interestingly, Trogus does not confuse Assyria with Babylonia. Moreover, he reports about weakness of central power in the reign of Semiramis son and tells that he and his successors communicated to their subjects through the magnates, which quite precisely reflects the situation in the reigns of Adad-nērārī III and his successors, when the Assyrian Empire was actually ruled by Šamši-ilu (Fuchs 2008).

183. See Schramm 1972; 1973, 112–13, contra this assumption; see Siddall 2013, 86–100, especially p. 99, in favor of it.

184. Fuchs 2008: 74–75.

185. See p. 275 n. 160, above.

studied together and not separately, as unfortunately still happens quite often in Assyriology. As has been shown, Assyrian royal women were not underrepresented in the pictorial and written sources. Moreover, the Neo-Assyrian period is, to the best of my knowledge, the only time in Mesopotamian history when we have identifiable monumental depictions of the queens. The survival of the memory of Sammu-rāmat, Naqī'a, and Šērū'a-ēṭirat in later noncuneiform sources reflects the fame surrounding their lives and proves that they were not at all invisible.

However, except for display inscriptions (which were no longer produced in the Sargonid period) and steles, none of the written sources were intentionally displayed for the public viewing of the masses. The purpose of the monumental pictorial sources was usually to target the large public of the palace's outer court and audience suites—or simply everybody, by means of royal steles and rock reliefs. But this was not so in the case of royal women. We can state with certainty that publicity was intended only in the case of the stele of Libbāli-šarrat. Statues in the round remained in publicly inaccessible temples. The Garden Scene and the reliefs of the passage to the Istar Temple adorned the walls of the palace's inner quarters. The provenance of the bronze relief depicting the king and Naqī'a is unknown, but it is generally believed to have been installed in a temple, probably in Babylon, and thus was inaccessible to the public.¹⁸⁶ Thus, images of royal women were usually not exposed for public view. As for Assyrian nonroyal women, except for the Garden Scene we do not know¹⁸⁷ of any other representations of them. The reason for this is probably that Assyrian women of status, be they royal or simply free, were to be protected from impudent gazes.

The famous paragraph 40 of the Middle Assyrian Laws declares that a free woman should be veiled when in public, as opposed to a slave girl or unmarried hierodule.¹⁸⁸ A veiled slave girl and even a man who did not turn her in were subject to severe punishments, which included facial mutilation and stripping off of their clothes. Captive or fugitive women soon to be slaves were very often represented on Assyrian palace reliefs, while Assyrian women remained hidden. Female dignity was perceived as vulnerable and violable through a woman's face being exposed for public observation, whether actually or by means of depiction. The right of discretion was reserved for free women and primarily for women of status.¹⁸⁹

In terms of royal women, a great change in their role in the Assyrian Empire—and, as a consequence, in their visibility—took place in the time of the Sargonids.

186. See Macgregor 2012: 111 with n. 89 for a bibliography concerning the opinion that it served as a divine throne dais. In my opinion, it could be also another kind of a monument (e.g., a stele of bronze) which may have been installed in the temple courtyard for public observation. However, Naqī'a was at that point not the king's spouse, but his mother (that is, not a young woman), and exposure of her image would not have been impudent.

187. This is the case except for probably one nonmonumental depiction of a woman applauding a triumphant king on a fragment of Assyrian-style ivory pyxis (ND 3599; 9th century B.C.E. Mallowan and Davies 1970: 18, pl. 5, no. 6). The kind of object might indicate that it belonged to a woman. S. L. Macgregor thinks that the females depicted on the reliefs of the passage leading toward the Istar Temple were not royal women but mere musicians (Macgregor 2012: 41–44). Female Assyrian(?) musicians(?) are depicted on the reliefs of Room E of the North Palace of Assurbanipal (Barnett 1976: pl. 14, slab 4[?] [BM 127370] and slab 5 [BM 118916]). The suggestion that this scene might represent a carnival will be developed elsewhere.

188. MAL A v 42–106; Roth 1995: 167–69, §40.

189. Compare van der Toorn 1995: 338. For exposure as degrading of status in the ancient Near East, see Cifarelli 1997: 220–23.

Reade attributed this change to the reign of Sennacherib,¹⁹⁰ but recently Svärd has suggested that it might have already started under the rule of Sargon II.¹⁹¹ The reason was, on one hand, Sargon's leaning on his immediate family in his quest to limit the power of magnates.¹⁹² On the other hand, it was connected with the elevation of the status of Aššur and the Sargonids' pursuit to make him the greatest god in the universe.¹⁹³ Together with Aššur, the status of the entire royal family was raised. In particular, the elevation of the god's spouse Mullissu directly influenced the status of the queen. Finally, attempts to sort out matters of succession also played a role, because the mother of the designated crown prince became important.¹⁹⁴ Strong personalities, such as Sammu-rāmat or Šamši-ilu, found their way to power both during periods of weakness of the central power and during absolute royal rule, but under the Sargonids there arose a kind of office of queenship.¹⁹⁵ Due to this, not only powerful females such as Naqī'a but also queens who did not have a real impact on Assyrian history and politics, such as Tašmētu-šarrat and Libbāli-šarrat, became visible. Being of female sex, the Neo-Assyrian queens were nonetheless gendered as male, not unlike their divine patron Ištar/Mullissu.

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190. Reade 1987.

191. Svärd 2015: 73.

192. May 2012a: 202; 2015; 2018: 494. J. Börker-Klähn points to the sealing of Tūta-napsum, the daughter of Sargon of Agade, as the first representation of a royal female in a mural crown (1997: 229–30 with pl. 14, fig. 5a). Taking into consideration Sargon II's allusions to his legendary namesake (May 2015: 103–5 with further literature), it is quite possible that the mural crown became part of the queens' attire already in his time.

193. Lambert 2013: 5; Frahm 2014: 212–13; May 2015: 80. However, I doubt that Mullissu became Aššur's spouse in this period, since she appeared as such already in the coronation ritual of Tukulti-Ninurta I (see p. 273 n. 149), who was probably the first to attempt at making Aššur the world's supreme deity.

194. See the succession treaties of Sennacherib and Esarhaddon (SAA 2 2, 5) and Lauinger 2012.

195. Svärd 2015: 39–86 discussed in detail the queen's household. However, it seems that starting with Sargon, the status of the queen was elevated together with degrading the status of the magnates (May 2015: 110). Moreover, from Naqī'a on the status of "office of the queen" was sufficiently upgraded.

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*Studying Gender
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SAANA SVÄRD AND AGNÈS GARCIA-VENTURA

EISENBRAUNS

University Park, Pennsylvania

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Abbreviations

General

A.	texts in the Assur collection of the Istanbul Arkeoloji Muzeleri, siglum
AO	museum siglum Louvre
Ass.	texts excavated in the German excavations at Assur, siglum
BM	British Museum
Curt.	Quintius Curtius Rufus, <i>Historiae Alexandri Magni</i>
D. S.	Diodorus Siculus, <i>Bibliotheca historica</i>
ED	Early Dynastic
Hdt.	Herodotus, <i>Historiae</i>
IB	Ishan Bahriyat, Isin excavation sigla
Iust.	Marcus Junianus Justinus, <i>Epitome Historiarum philippicarum Pompei Trogi</i>
K	texts in the Kuyunjik Collection of the British Museum, siglum
MAL	Middle Assyrian Laws
ND	field numbers of tablets excavated at Nimrud
OB	Old Babylonian
Pomp. Trog.	Gaius Pompeus Trogus
Str.	Strabo, <i>Geographica</i>
VAT	museum siglum of the Vorderasiatisches Museum, Berlin

Reference Works

AHw	W. von Soden, <i>Akkadisches Handwörterbuch</i> . Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz, 1959–81
AMT	R. C. Thompson, <i>Assyrian Medical Texts from the Originals of the British Museum</i> . London: Humphrey Milford Oxford University Press, 1923
ARM 26 I/1	J.-M. Durand, <i>Archives épistolaires de Mari 1/1</i> . Paris: Éditions Recherche sur les Civilisations, 1988
ASV	T. C. Mitchell and A. Searight, <i>Catalogue of the Western Asiatic Seals in the British Museum: Stamp Seals</i> , part 3: <i>Impressions of Stamp Seals on Cuneiform Tablets, Clay Bullae, and Jar Handles</i> . Leiden: Brill, 2008
BAM	F. Köcher, <i>Die babylonisch-assyrische Medizin in Texten und Untersuchungen Vol. 1–6</i> . Berlin: de Gruyter, 1963–80
BAP	B. Meissner, <i>Beiträge zum altbabylonischen Privatrecht</i> . Leipzig: Hinrichs, 1893
BASOR	<i>Bulletin of the American Schools of Oriental Research</i>
BDTNS	Database of Neo-Sumerian Texts. Online: http://bdtns.filol.csic.es/
BRM 1	A. T. Clay, <i>Babylonian Business Transactions of the First Millennium B.C.: Babylonian Records in the Library of J. Pierpont Morgan</i> . Part 1. New York, 1912
BWL	W. G. Lambert, <i>Babylonian Wisdom Literature</i> . Oxford: Clarendon 1960
CAD	Ignace J. Gelb et al., editors. <i>The Assyrian Dictionary of the Oriental Institute of the University of Chicago</i> . 21 vols. (A–Z). Chicago: Oriental Institute, 1956–2011

- CAT M. Dietrich, O. Loretz, and J. Sanmartín, *The Cuneiform Alphabetic Texts from Ugarit, Ras Ibn Hani and Other Places (KTU: second, enlarged edition)*. Münster: Ugarit-Verlag, 1996
- CDA J. Black et al., *A Concise Dictionary of Akkadian*. 2nd ed. Santag 5. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz, 2000
- CDLI Cuneiform Digital Library Initiative. Online: <http://cdli.ucla.edu/>
- CM Cuneiform Monographs
- CRRAI *Compte rendu of the 47th Rencontre Assyriologique Internationale*
- CT 4 E. A. W. Budge, *Cuneiform Texts from Babylonian Tablets in the British Museum, Part IV*. London: British Museum, 1898
- CT 6 E. A. W. Budge, *Cuneiform Texts from Babylonian Tablets in the British Museum, Part VI*. London: British Museum, 1898
- CT 8 E. A. W. Budge, *Cuneiform Texts from Babylonian Tablets in the British Museum, Part VIII*. London: British Museum, 1899
- CT 18 E. A. W. Budge, *Cuneiform Texts from Babylonian Tablets in the British Museum, Part XVIII*. London: British Museum, 1964
- CT 39 C. J. Gadd *Cuneiform Texts from Babylonian Tablets in the British Museum, Part XXXIX*. London: British Museum, 1926
- CT 45 T. G. Pinches, *Cuneiform Texts from Babylonian Tablets in the British Museum, Part XLV, Old-Babylonian Business Documents*. London: British Museum, 1964
- CT 47 H. H. Figulla, *Cuneiform Texts from Babylonian Tablets in the British Museum, Part XLVII, Old-Babylonian Naditu Records*. London: British Museum, 1967
- CT 48 J. J. Finkelstein, *Cuneiform Texts from Babylonian Tablets in the British Museum, Part XLVIII, Old-Babylonian Legal Documents*. London: British Museum, 1968
- CUSAS Cornell University Studies in Assyriology and Sumerology
- ePSD *The Pennsylvania Sumerian Dictionary*. Online: psd.museum.upenn.edu
- ETCSL Electronic Text Corpus of Sumerian Literature. Online: <http://etcsl.orinst.ox.ac.uk>
- FAOS Freiburger Altorientalische Studien
- GBAO Göttinger Beiträge zum Alten Orient
- HES Heidelberger Emesal Studien
- HSS V E. Chiera, *Excavations at Nuzi, vol. 1: Texts of Varied Contents*. Harvard Semitic Series V. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1929
- Igituḫ B. Landsberger and O. R. Gurney, "igi-duḫ-a = tāmartu, Short Version." *Archiv für Orientforschung* 18 (1957–58): 81–86
- JCS Supplement *Journal of Cuneiform Studies Supplement*
- JEN 3 E. Chiera, *Joint Expedition with the Iraq Museum at Nuzi, vol. 3: Exchange and Security Documents*. American Schools of Oriental Research, Publications of the Baghdad School: Texts 3. Paris: Geuthner, 1931
- JEN 7 E. R. Lacheman and M. P. Maidman, *Studies on the Civilization and Culture of Nuzi and the Hurrians*. Vol. 3. Joint Expedition with the Iraq Museum at Nuzi, Miscellaneous Texts 7. Winona Lake, IN: Eisenbrauns, 1989
- KADP F. Köcher, *Keilschrifttexte zur assyrisch-babylonischen Drogen- und Pflanzenkunde. Texte der Serien uru.an.na: maltakal, HAR. ra: hubullu und Ú GAR-sú*. Berlin Akademie-Verlag, 1955
- KAR E. Ebeling, *Keilschrifttexte aus Assur religiösen Inhalts*. Leipzig: Hinrichs, 1915–23
- KTU M. Dietrich, O. Loretz, and J. Sanmartín, editors. *Die Keilalphabetischen Texte aus Ugarit*. Alter Orient und Altes Testament 24. Kevelaer: Butzon & Bercker / Neukirchen-Vluyn: Neukirchener Verlag, 1976

- LIMC* *Lexicon iconographicum mythologiae classicae*. Düsseldorf: Artemis, 1981–2009
- LKA* E. Ebeling, *Literarische Keilschrifttexte aus Assur*. Berlin: Akademie-Verlag, 1953
- LTBA* W. von Soden, *Die lexikalischen Tafelserien der Babylonier und Assyrer in den Berliner Museen*, vol. 2: *Die akkadischen Synonymenlisten*. Berlin: Staatliche Museen zu Berlin, Vorderasiatische Abteilung, 1933
- MAD* I. J. Gelb, *Materials for the Assyrian Dictionary*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1952–70
- malku = šarru* A. D. Kilmer, “The First Tablet of *malku = šarru* together with Its Explicit Version.” *Journal of the American Oriental Society* 83 (1963): 421–46
- MC* Mesopotamian Civilizations
- MHEOP* Mesopotamian History and Environment, Occasional Publications
- MHET* L. Dekiere, *Old Babylonian Real Estate Documents from Sippar in the British Museum—Parts 1–6 (= Mesopotamian History and Environment Texts II 1–6)*. Wetteren: Cultura, 1994–97
- MSL 12* M. Civil, *The Series lú = ša and Related Texts*. Materials for the Sumerian Lexicon 12. Rome: Pontifical Biblical Institute, 1969
- MSL 17* A. Cavigneaux, H. Güterbock, and M. Roth, *The Series Erim-huš = anantu and An-ta-gál = šaqû*. Materials for the Sumerian Lexicon 17. Rome: Pontifical Biblical Institute, 1985
- Murgud B* *see* *MSL 12*
- NABU* *Nouvelles Assyriologique Brèves et Utilitaires*
- NPN* I. J. Gelb, P. M. Purves, and A. A. MacRae, *Nuzi Personal Names*. Oriental Institute Publications 57. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1943
- OBO* *Orbis Biblicus et Orientalis*
- OED* *Oxford English Dictionary*. 2nd ed. 20 vols. Oxford: Clarendon / New York: Oxford University Press, 1989
- OLA* *Orientalia Lovaniensia Analecta*
- Oracc* The Open Richly Annotated Cuneiform Corpus. Online: <http://oracc.museum.upenn.edu/>
- PIHANS* Publications de l’Institut historique-archéologique néerlandais de Stamboul
- RAI* Rencontre Assyriologique Internationale
- RIMA 1* A. K. Grayson, *Assyrian Rulers of the Third and Second Millennia B.C. (to 1115 B.C.)*. Royal Inscriptions of Mesopotamia, Assyrian Periods 1. Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 1987
- RIMA 2* A. K. Grayson, *Assyrian Rulers of the Early First Millennium B.C., Volume 1 (1114–859 B.C.)*. Royal Inscriptions of Mesopotamia, Assyrian Periods 2. Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 1991
- RIMA 3* A. K. Grayson, *Assyrian Rulers of the Early First Millennium B.C., Volume 2 (858–745 B.C.)*. Royal Inscriptions of Mesopotamia, Assyrian Periods 3. Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 1996
- RIME* Royal Inscriptions of Mesopotamia, Early Periods
- RIME 3/1* D. O. Edzard, *Gudea and His Dynasty*. Royal Inscriptions of Mesopotamia, Early Periods 3/1. Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 1997
- RIME 3/2* D. Frayne, *Ur III Period*. Royal Inscriptions of Mesopotamia, Early Periods 3/2. Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 1997
- RIME 4* D. Frayne, *Old Babylonian Period (2003–1595 BC)*. Royal Inscriptions of Mesopotamia, Early Periods 4. Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 1990
- RINAP 4* Leichty, E., 2011. *The Royal Inscriptions of Esarhaddon, King of Assyria (680–669 B.C.)*. Winona Lake IN: The Royal Inscriptions of the Neo-Assyrian Period 4. Eisenbrauns.

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- RINAP 3/2 A. K. Grayson and J. R. Novotny., 2014. *The Royal Inscriptions of Sennacherib, King of Assyria (704-681 BC)*, Part 2. The Royal Inscriptions of the Neo-Assyrian Period 3/2. Winona Lake, IN: Eisenbrauns, 2014
- RIA *Reallexikon der Assyriologie und Vorderasiatischen Archäologie*
- SAA State Archives of Assyria
- SAA 1 S. Parpola, *The Correspondence of Sargon II*, part 1: *Letters from Assyria and the West*. State Archives of Assyria 1. Helsinki: Helsinki University Press, 1987
- SAA 2 S. Parpola and K. Watanabe. *Neo-Assyrian Treaties and Loyalty Oaths*. State Archives of Assyria 2. Helsinki: Helsinki University Press, 1988.
- SAA 3 A. Livingstone, *Court Poetry and Literary Miscellanea*. Helsinki: State Archives of Assyria 3. Helsinki University Press, 1989
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- SAA 17 M. Dietrich, *The Babylonian Correspondence of Sargon and Sennacherib*. State Archives of Assyria 17. Helsinki: Helsinki University Press, 2003
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- SAA 20 S. Parpola, *Assyrian Royal Rituals and Cultic Texts*. State Archives of Assyria 20. Helsinki: Neo-Assyrian Text Corpus Project, 2017
- SAAB *State Archives of Assyria Bulletin*
- SAAS State Archives of Assyria Studies
- SAG A and SAG B M. Civil, O. R. Gurney, and D. A. Kennedy, *The Sag-Tablet, Lexical Texts in the Ashmolean Museum, Middle Babylonian Grammatical Texts, Miscellaneous Texts*. Materials for the Sumerian Lexicon Supplementary Series 1. Rome: Pontifical Biblical Institute, 1986
- SAOC Studies in Ancient Oriental Civilization
- SFS V. Scheil, *Une saison de fouilles à Sippar, Institut français d'archéologie orientale*. Cairo: Imprimerie de l'Institut français d'archéologie orientale, 1902
- SHCANE Studies in the History and Culture of the Ancient Near East

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- SpTU* 3 E. von Weiher, *Spätbabylonische Texte aus Uruk III*. Ausgrabungen der Deutschen Forschungsgemeinschaft in Uruk-Warka 12. Berlin: Mann, 1988
- SpTU* 5 E. von Weiher, *Uruk. Teil 5, Spätbabylonische Texte aus dem Planquadrat U 18*. Mainz am Rhein: von Zabern 1998
- STT* O. R. Gurney, *The Sultantepe Tablets Vol. 1–2*. Ankara: Occasional Publications of the British Institute of Archaeology in Ankara, 1957–64
- TCL* I F. Thureau-Dangin, *Lettres et contrats de l'époque de la première dynastie babylonienne*. Paris: Geuthner, 1910
- UDB* J.-L. Cunchillos, J.-P. Vita, and J.-Á. Zamora, *The Texts of the Ugaritic Data Bank*. Vol. 1. Piscataway, NJ: Gorgias, 2003
- UE* L. Woolley and M. Mallowan, *The Old Babylonian Period*. Ur Excavations 7. London: British Museum Publications, 1976
- VS* Vorderasiatische Schriftdenkmäler der (Königlichen) Museen zu Berlin
- WOO* Wiener Offene Orientalistik
- YBC* Yale Babylonian Collection
- YOS* 10 A. Goetze, *Old Babylonian Omen Texts*. Yale Oriental Series, Babylonian Texts 10. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press, 1947
- ZTT* S. Parpola, "Cuneiform Texts from Ziyaret Tepe (Tuşhan), 2002–2003." *State Archives of Assyria Bulletin* 17 (2008): 1–113